

Diabesity and mood disorders: Multiple links through the microbiota-gut-brain axis

Aitak Farzi^a, Ahmed M. Hassan^a, Geraldine Zenz^a, Peter Holzer^{a,b,*}

^a Research Unit of Translational Neurogastroenterology, Division of Pharmacology, Otto Loewi Research Centre, Medical University of Graz, Universitätsplatz 4, A-8010 Graz, Austria

^b BioTechMed-Graz, Mozartgasse 12, A-8010 Graz, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Anxiety
Brain-derived neurotrophic factor
Endocannabinoids
Depression
Diabetes
Diet restriction
 γ -Amino butyric acid
Glucagon-like peptide
Gut-brain axis
Gut microbiota
Lipopolysaccharide
Neuropeptide Y
Obesity
Peptide YY
Short-chain fatty acids
Tryptophan metabolites

ABSTRACT

The global prevalence of diabesity is on the rise, and the clinical, social and economic health burden arising from this epidemic is aggravated by a significant co-morbidity of diabesity with neuropsychiatric disease, particularly depression. Importantly, not only is the prevalence of mood disorders elevated in patients with type 2 diabetes, depressed patients are also more prone to develop diabetes. This reciprocal relationship calls for a molecular and systemic analysis of diabesity-brain interactions to guide preventive and therapeutic strategies. The analysis we are presenting in this review is modelled on the microbiota-gut-brain axis, which provides the brain with information from the gut not only via the nervous system, but also via a continuous stream of microbial, endocrine, metabolic and immune messages. This communication network offers important clues as to how obesity and diabetes could target the brain to provoke neuropsychiatric disease. There is emerging evidence that the gut microbiota is orchestrating a multiplicity of bodily functions that are intimately related to the immune, metabolic and nervous systems and that gut dysbiosis spoils the homeostasis between these systems. In our article we highlight two groups of molecular links that seem to have a significant bearing on the impact of diabesity on the brain. On the one hand, we focus on microbiota-related metabolites such as short-chain fatty acids, tryptophan metabolites, immune stimulants and endocannabinoids that are likely to play a mediator role. On the other hand, we discuss signalling molecules that operate primarily in the brain, specifically neuropeptide Y, brain-derived neurotrophic factor and γ -amino butyric acid, that are disturbed by microbial factors, obesity and diabetes and are relevant to mental illness. Finally, we address the usefulness of diet-related interventions to suspend the deleterious relationship between diabesity and mood disorders.

1. Diabesity and neuropsychiatric disease: missing links to be identified

Nutrition-related and metabolic diseases have long been known to be associated with neuropsychiatric disorders. Epidemiological studies have shown that unbalanced nutrition (e.g., refined high-energy food rich in sugar and fat) enhances the risk of developing depression (Jacka et al., 2011; Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2012) while a healthy diet has a protective effect (Jacka et al., 2011, 2017; Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2013). However, the precise mechanisms linking diabesity with neuropsychiatric disease have thus far been little studied, and the relevance of dietary improvement to the management of patients with major depression and other mental disorders is being only gradually recognized (Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2013; Jacka et al., 2017). The study of this relationship is encompassed in the aims of the International

Society for Nutritional Psychiatry Research (www.isnpr.org). In addition, the last decades have seen a huge increment in knowledge on how peripheral organs, notably the gastrointestinal tract, communicate with the central nervous system. The delineation of the gut-brain axis has shown that the brain receives information from the gut not only via the nervous system, but also via a continuous stream of microbial, endocrine, metabolic and immune factors. This complex communication network serves as a model that may guide the analysis of the potential relationships between obesity, diabetes and neuropsychiatric disease.

Although the molecular basis of the interactions between diabesity and perturbations of brain function is gradually emerging, there are many missing links that remain to be identified. A synopsis of the available information suggests that diabesity-related mental illness develops when homeostasis in the interactions between gut microbiota, immune system, metabolic system and brain is disturbed. With this

* Corresponding author. Experimental Neurogastroenterology, Research Unit of Translational Neurogastroenterology, Division of Pharmacology, Otto Loewi Research Centre, Medical University of Graz, Universitätsplatz 4, A-8010 Graz, Austria.

E-mail address: peter.holzer@medunigraz.at (P. Holzer).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mam.2018.11.003>

Received 8 August 2018; Received in revised form 30 October 2018; Accepted 30 November 2018

Available online 13 December 2018

0098-2997/ © 2018 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

framework in mind, we highlight a number of molecular factors generated by the gut microbiota, on the one hand, and cerebral signalling molecules altered in obesity and diabetes, on the other hand, as potential links in the interaction between diabetes and mood disorders, particularly depression. Given the complexities of this relationship, we do not attempt to be exhaustive but rather focus on select signalling molecules, the actions of which explain how obesity, diabetes and brain dysfunction may converge. Some obvious candidates are spared because, for instance, the roles of insulin (see chapter by J.C. Brüning and colleagues) and leptin (see chapter by S. Bouret and colleagues) in regulating cerebral function are covered by other articles of this special issue on 'Molecular Aspects of Signalling in Diabetes'. We conclude our review by discussing the potential of diet-related interventions to interrupt the deleterious relationship between diabetes and mood disorders.

2. Associations between diabetes, stress and depression

2.1. Clinical studies

Both diabetes and obesity carry an increased risk for mental health problems, but this relationship does not seem to be a road in one direction. Not only is the prevalence of depression elevated in patients with type 2 diabetes (Wing et al., 1990; Semenkovich et al., 2015), depressed patients are also more prone to develop diabetes later in life (Kawakami et al., 1999; Eaton et al., 1996; Semenkovich et al., 2015). Depression shows in fact high rates of co-morbidity with diabetes. Thus, people suffering from depression have a 32–41% increased risk of diabetes, and 8–15% of patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes are diagnosed with depressive disorders (Holt et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2015; de Groot et al., 2016). In other terms, the prevalence rate of depression is more than three times higher in people with type 1 diabetes and nearly twice as high in people with type 2 diabetes (Roy and Lloyd, 2012). The enhanced risk of developing depression is not only confined to patients with diagnosed diabetes, but also extends to patients with undiagnosed diabetes and pre-diabetic patients who face a moderately increased risk of depression (Chen et al., 2016). It should not go unnoticed here that people suffering from other mental illnesses like schizophrenia also carry an increased risk to develop diabetes. While the mechanisms linking schizophrenia to diabetes are still obscure, several studies suggest a connection between antipsychotic drug treatment and changes in glucose metabolism (Mukherjee et al., 1996; Ryan and Thakore, 2002; Holt et al., 2005; Kowalchuk et al., 2018).

In a comprehensive consideration of the triangle of interactions between obesity, diabetes and mental illness it becomes evident that obesity is able to increase the risk of several neuropsychiatric disorders including depression, anxiety disorders, schizophrenia and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder up to 70% whereas, vice versa, the risk to become obese can be increased 2- to 3-fold in individuals suffering from mental disorders (De Hert et al., 2011; Avila et al., 2015). Although a review of primarily cross-sectional studies provided at first rather weak evidence for an association between obesity and depression in women, but not men (Atlantis and Baker, 2008), later meta-analyses of longitudinal studies revealed a clear co-morbidity of obesity with depression and anxiety disorders in both males and females (Luppino et al., 2010; Mannan et al., 2016; Jung et al., 2017).

As alluded to before, some of the studies also disclosed a reciprocal relationship between depression and obesity: not only does obesity increase the risk of depression, depression is also predictive for developing obesity. This association seems, however, to be stronger in female than in male adolescents (Mannan et al., 2016). As regards children, a recent meta-analysis found that, unlike male children, obese female children (aged < 18 years) have a significantly higher risk of depression compared to normal-weight female children, this risk persisting into adulthood (Sutaria et al., 2018). As both diabetes and obesity are frequently related to unhealthy eating habits, it is not unexpected that

low-quality nutrition (high-energy food rich in sugar and fat) also bears a significant risk of depression (Jacka et al., 2011; Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2012), while a balanced diet has a protective effect (Jacka et al., 2011, 2017; Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2013). Although the co-morbidity of obesity and depression has been most investigated, epidemiological studies also attest to an association between diabetes and anxiety disorders, on the one hand, and between obesity and anxiety disorders, on the other hand (Garipey et al., 2010; Smith et al., 2013).

Another factor that needs to be considered in the relationship between diabetes and mental disorders is chronic stress. Depression and stressful life events increase the risk of obesity and metabolic syndrome (Räikkönen et al., 2007; Williams et al., 2009; Luppino et al., 2010; Vogelzangs et al., 2008). A high rate of daily stressors is associated with diminished energy expenditure and increased insulin secretion, changes that provide an explanation how stress can alter metabolic responses to high-fat meals in ways that promote obesity (Kiecolt-Glaser et al., 2015). Noteworthy, chronic stress can have a bidirectional effect on eating and body weight, as some subjects will eat less and lose weight while others eat more and gain weight (Razzoli and Bartolomucci, 2016). Stress eaters present with increased levels of cortisol, total cholesterol/high density lipoprotein and nocturnal insulin (Epel et al., 2004). However, the relationship between stress and diabetes is complex, because not only stress-induced chronic overeating and a stress-related unhealthy lifestyle enhance the risk of type 2 diabetes, but also strong psychological stress including burnout *per se* can reinforce the risk of diabetes through increases in blood pressure, insulin secretion and inflammatory processes (Melamed et al., 2006; Heraclides et al., 2009; Harris et al., 2017).

2.2. Preclinical studies

In an attempt to analyse the pathophysiological mechanisms that link diabetes to perturbations of brain function and behaviour, several preclinical studies have been able to show that animal models of diabetes and/or obesity are associated with a phenotype of depression-like and/or anxiety-like behaviour. The most consistent finding of these studies is that experimentally induced obesity and/or diabetes are associated with a depression-like phenotype. This relationship is seen when rodents are treated with an overtly obesogenic high-fat diet (HFD) for a prolonged period of time (Sharma and Fulton, 2013; Duthheil et al., 2016; Zemdegs et al., 2016; Hassan et al., 2018), while the results are more variable when lower concentrations of fat or shorter treatment protocols are used. Under these conditions, a moderate high-fat diet may even have the opposite effect, i.e., reducing depression-like behaviour induced by stress (Maniam and Morris, 2010; Finger et al., 2011).

The studies addressing a potential influence of HFD on anxiety-like behaviour have produced even less consistent results, as anxiogenic, anxiolytic or no effects at all have been reported (Maniam and Morris, 2010; Finger et al., 2011; Sharma and Fulton, 2013; Hassan et al., 2018). This discrepancy in the findings may to some extent be related to the duration of treatment with HFD (Gainey et al., 2016), but may also reflect that some mice are resilient to the metabolic and behavioural phenotypes of obesity (Sweeney et al., 2017).

The adverse effect of stress on the metabolic system has been extensively modelled in animal studies, with results that resemble those seen in humans. In rodents, several stress paradigms can exaggerate obesity, adiposity, insulin resistance, and dyslipidaemia (Sanghez et al., 2013; Lin et al., 2015; Razzoli et al., 2015a, 2015b, 2017). As in humans, not all animals exposed to stress develop metabolic disorders. For example, subordinate mice were found to be vulnerable to weight gain and metabolic effects of psychological stress, whereas dominant mice were resilient to these perturbations (Sanghez et al., 2013). Psychological stress increases glucocorticoid levels and caloric intake, dysregulates insulin secretion and induces visceral obesity (Rosmond, 2003; Dallman, 2010). Besides the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA)

Fig. 1. Pathways involved in the communication between gut and brain. The graph shows multiple interactive information carriers that include microbiota-derived signals (e.g., lipopolysaccharide and related immune stimulants, tryptophan metabolites and short chain fatty acids), immune cell-derived signals (e.g., pro-inflammatory cytokines), gut hormones (e.g., glucagon-like peptides and peptide YY), and vagal and spinal afferent neurons.

axis, several neuropeptides and gut hormones are thought to be involved in the stress-induced weight gain and associated metabolic disorder, including agouti-related peptide (AgrP), neuropeptide Y (NPY), orexin, ghrelin, GLP-1 and PYY (Diz-Chaves et al., 2016; Razzoli and Bartolomucci, 2016).

3. Communication networks between gut and brain

In order to comprehend the complex interactions between gut and brain it is important to consider some basic information on the communication network that exists between gastrointestinal microbiota, mucosa, endocrine system, immune system and enteric nervous system, on the one hand, and the brain, on the other hand. There are at least 5 information carriers (Fig. 1) that signal information from the gut to the brain: gut microbiota-derived molecules, immune mediators, gut hormones, vagal afferent neurons, and spinal afferent neurons (Holzer et al., 2017; Farzi et al., 2018). As the interaction between gut and brain is bidirectional, there are also at least 4 information carriers that signal from the central nervous system to the digestive tract: parasympathetic efferent neurons, sympathetic efferent neurons, neuroendocrine factors involving the adrenal medulla, and neuroendocrine factors involving the adrenal cortex (Holzer et al., 2017). These abundant signalling systems cover a wide range of external and internal stimuli that impact on the digestive tract. In addition, they differ in the sensitivities to the various stimuli, in the time scale they transmit information to the brain, in the target regions they address in the brain, and in the molecular entities they use for signalling. Additional relays that modify gut-brain communication include the blood-brain barrier (BBB), the emerging implications of the microglia and distinct brain circuits that distribute the information the brain receives from the periphery to specific output centres.

Of the plethora of molecular entities involved in gut-brain signalling we highlight only a few examples in this introductory part of the chapter, with more specific information given in other parts of the review. The 5 gut-brain information carriers depicted in Fig. 1 involve circulation-based (endocrine-like) and neuronal communication routes, and it is important to consider that these systems do not operate in isolation but are closely interrelated with each other (Holzer et al., 2017). For instance, microbial metabolites such as microbe-associated patterns (MAMPs) and pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) can target both endocrine and immune cells in the

gastrointestinal tract as well as sensory neurons, especially those of the vagus nerve (Holzer et al., 2017). Another example is posed by the short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) which are generated from otherwise indigestible carbohydrate fibres through microbial fermentation. Like MAMPs and PAMPs, SCFAs are multi-target messengers that act on gastrointestinal endocrine, mucosal and immune cells as well as on the BBB and the cerebral microglia (Erny et al., 2015; Rooks and Garrett, 2016). Most of the cellular effects of SCFAs are mediated by G protein-coupled receptors (GPRs) termed free fatty acid receptors (FFARs) that are expressed by a variety of cells in the gut and brain (Erny et al., 2015; Rooks and Garrett, 2016; Holzer et al., 2017).

The interaction between the different information carriers of the gut-brain axis is further exemplified by the ability of SCFAs to release the gut hormones peptide YY (PYY), glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and GLP-2 (Samuel et al., 2008; Bindels et al., 2013). Through this action, enteroendocrine cells distribute messages of the gut microbiota not only within the alimentary canal but also to distant organs including the brain. Following their release from enteroendocrine L cells, PYY and GLP-1 not only inhibit gastric motility and modify glucose homeostasis but also facilitate satiety and alter emotional and cognitive behaviour (Holzer and Farzi, 2018). In addition, enteroendocrine cells are involved in circulation-independent ways of gut-brain communication, given that misfolded α -synuclein can be transferred to the brain through direct connections between enteroendocrine cells and neural circuits, thus contributing to the pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease (Chandra et al., 2017). The effect of PYY and GLP-1 on mood and emotional-affective behaviour is not only mediated via hormone delivery through the circulatory route but also by modifying the activity of afferent vagal neurons (Field et al., 2010; Holzer et al., 2015). The role of the vagus nerve in the signalling of microbial, endocrine and immune signals to the brain is consistent with its composition, the majority of the vagal axons being afferent nerve fibres (Holzer, 2008). This afferent role of the vagus nerve is relevant not only to the autonomic regulation of digestion and energy balance but also to interoception which refers to the integrated representation of the internal physiological state in the brain (Craig, 2002; Mayer, 2011). Apart from the sensations of pain, nausea, gastrointestinal discomfort and tension, urgency, hunger and thirst, interoception may go consciously unnoticed although it impacts on emotional-affective and cognitive processes.

4. Mechanistic links between diabetes, brain dysfunction and mood disorders

The co-morbidity between unhealthy eating habits, obesity and diabetes with depression and other neuropsychiatric disorders raises the question as to the pathophysiological mechanisms that link these pathologies together. In this review we highlight a select number of factors which are targeted in parallel by gut microbiota disturbances, obesity and diabetes and which have the potential to perturb brain function and emotional-affective behaviour (Fig. 2). There is emerging evidence that the gut microbiota is orchestrating a multiplicity of bodily functions that are intimately related to the immune, metabolic and nervous systems and that gut dysbiosis spoils the homeostasis between these systems. In this article, we focus on three classes of microbiota-related metabolites, namely SCFAs, tryptophan metabolites and immune stimulants, that are likely to play a mediator role. We then turn to signalling molecules that operate primarily in the central nervous system, specifically NPY, brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and γ -amino butyric acid (GABA), which are challenged by microbial factors, obesity and diabetes and, when disturbed, impair brain functions that are relevant to mood disorders (Fig. 2).

We want to emphasize that this list of candidate factors interconnecting the triangle of obesity, diabetes and neuropsychiatric disease is by no means exhaustive, yet is thought to delineate a framework on which to guide further research efforts. As we concentrate on the relationship between diabetes and mood disorders, we do not consider

Fig. 2. Mechanistic links between gut microbiota, gut mucosa and gut immune system, on the one hand, and obesity, diabetes and brain dysfunction, on the other hand, underlying diabetes-associated neuropsychiatric disease. The graph shows that the triangle of obesity, diabetes and brain dysfunction is targeted by a disturbed gut microbiota (gut dysbiosis) through microbiota-derived factors which spoil the homeostasis between immune, metabolic and nervous system. In the periphery, microbiota-derived metabolites such as short-chain fatty acids (SCFA), gut hormones released by SCFA, tryptophan metabolites and immune mediators have a parallel impact on obesity, diabetes and brain dysfunction. In the brain, signalling systems including neuropeptide Y (NPY), brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), γ -amino butyric acid (GABA) and corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF) are perturbed in discrete circuits, giving rise to mood disorders such as depression. Obesity and diabetes also signal to the brain via leptin and insulin, respectively, and other messengers to disturb cognitive performance, an issue that is not discussed in this review. The mechanisms of action whereby insulin and leptin contribute to the interaction between microbiota, diabetes and brain are covered in the chapters by J.C. Brüning and colleagues and S. Bouret and colleagues. Importantly, obesity and diabetes also exert a negative feedback on the gut microbiota to cause dysbiosis. \uparrow Stimulation, \downarrow inhibition. Abbreviations: GLP-1, glucagon-like peptide-1; IPA, indole-3-propionic acid; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; NOD, nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing protein; PYY, peptide YY.

important signalling molecules that link obesity and diabetes primarily with cognitive disorders including Alzheimer's disease. Leptin, adipokines and other mediators of adipose tissue (Farr et al., 2015) as well as insulin (Cholerton et al., 2013) play a major role in these interactions and in the manifestation of diabetes-associated cognitive impairment. The implications of insulin and leptin in the impact of diabetes on neurological disorders are discussed in detail in other chapters of this special issue on 'Molecular Aspects of Signalling in Diabetes' (see the article on insulin by J.C. Brüning and colleagues and the article on leptin by S. Bouret and colleagues).

Emerging evidence indicates that a variety of drugs used to treat diabetes can also impact on the gut microbiome as well as on

behaviour and mental health. Metformin, for instance, has a distinct effect on the gut microbiota, which appears to be relevant to the clinical benefits of the drug (Sun et al., 2018). Other antidiabetic drugs such as sitagliptin, liraglutide and pioglitazone have been reported in some, but not all, studies to improve emotional-affective and cognitive behaviour in preclinical models of mental disease (Kamble et al., 2016; Magdy et al., 2017; Hassan et al., 2018; Weina et al., 2018) as well as in patients with mood disorders (Colle et al., 2017; Mansur et al., 2017). On the other hand, psychoactive medications (e.g., antidepressant and antipsychotic drugs) can have adverse effects on the gut bacteria (Le Bastard et al., 2018; Maier et al., 2018). While these implications of drugs shed further light on the interaction between gut microbiota, diabetes and mental health, they need also be considered as confounding factors in the interpretation of clinical data obtained from patients under pharmacotherapy.

4.1. Gut microbiota

Given that diet is one of the major environmental factors shaping the composition of the gastrointestinal microbial community, several studies have analysed the role of the microbiota in, e.g., diet-associated depression. Specifically, a disturbance in the gut microbial community (dysbiosis), a dysfunctional intestinal mucosal barrier and persistent low-grade immune activation are being discussed as potential factors (Slyepchenko et al., 2017). There is indeed ample evidence that the gut microbial community is altered in diabetes as well as in depression. More specifically, both obese and diabetic subjects have a different composition of the intestinal microbiome compared to lean subjects (Million et al., 2013). Animal studies indicate a causal involvement of the microbiome, since germ-free or antibiotic-treated mice are protected from obesity and a metabolic syndrome-like state in response to an obesogenic diet (Bäckhed et al., 2007; Cani et al., 2008; Rabot et al., 2010). Moreover, modification of the gut microbial community with probiotics reduces diet-related weight gain and insulin resistance in rodents, while in humans there is relatively weak evidence for the efficacy of probiotics in reducing weight and improving glycaemic control (Diamant et al., 2011; Park and Bae, 2015; Samah et al., 2016).

In a similar line, patients suffering from depression present with an altered composition of the intestinal microbiome (Naseribafrouei et al., 2014; Jiang et al., 2015; Kelly et al., 2016; Zheng et al., 2016). A causal involvement of a disturbed intestinal microbiota in the aetiology of depression is supported by the findings that microbiota transfer from depressed patients is in fact able to induce a depression-like phenotype in the recipient rodents (Kelly et al., 2016; Zheng et al., 2016). In addition, there is also experimental evidence that the disturbances of emotional-affective behaviour caused by HFD-related diabetes require the presence of the intestinal microbiome. Thus, Bruce-Keller et al. (2015) showed that the transfer of caecal contents from HFD-treated mice to antibiotic-treated mice induced anxiety-like behaviour and attenuated cognitive performance in the recipient animals. The behavioural changes were associated with blunted expression of intestinal barrier markers, increased levels of circulating endotoxin and increased expression of inflammatory markers in intestine, lymphocytes and brain. These observations indicate that the HFD-disturbed gut microbiota perturbs behaviour via intestinal barrier dysfunction, MAMP delivery, and peripheral as well as cerebral inflammation. This implication of the microbiome has been confirmed by the ability of antibiotics to block the anxiety-related behaviour induced by HFD, an effect that is associated with enhancement of glucose tolerance and insulin receptor sensitivity in the brain (Soto et al., 2018).

4.2. Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) as links between the gut microbiota and diabetes

As alluded to before, SCFAs are produced by the gut microbiota through fermentation of indigestible fibres. Although some evidence

indicates that SCFAs can promote obesity, there is emerging information that SCFAs are bacterial metabolites that reduce obesity and improve insulin sensitivity (Herrema et al., 2017). The SCFAs comprising acetic, *n*-butyric and propionic acid are ligands of GPR43 (FFAR2) and GPR41 (FFAR3) (Brown et al., 2003). In addition, butyrate has a low affinity for GPR109A (or hydroxycarboxylic acid receptor) (Thangaraju et al., 2009). While these receptors are regarded to be the main mediators of the biological effects of SCFAs, SCFA-induced prevention of HFD-induced obesity and insulin resistance has been proposed to depend on a GPR-independent mechanism. Specifically, SCFAs increase oxidative metabolism in liver and adipose tissue through a mechanism involving peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ and AMP kinase (den Besten et al., 2015).

One of the mechanisms underlying the GPR-dependent effects of SCFAs is release of the satiety factors GLP-1 and PYY from enteroendocrine L-cells of the intestinal epithelium, which are crucial signalling factors that mediate some of the systemic and cerebral effects of SCFAs (Groen et al., 2018). The incretin effect of GLP-1, which results in enhanced insulin secretion, has led to the development of various GLP-1 receptor agonists for the treatment of diabetes (Tran et al., 2017). A recent analysis of the peptide's incretin effect has revealed that insulin secretion in response to GLP-1 depends on the microbiota-gut-brain axis (Grasset et al., 2017). This mechanism was discovered when the mechanism of GLP-1 resistance induced by HFD was analysed in detail. The pertinent data indicate that HFD disturbs the microbiota composition of the ileum, which impairs nitric oxide production in enteric neurons and consequently blunts gut-brain signalling (Grasset et al., 2017).

Besides GLP-1, PYY also plays an important role in the broad context of diabetes (Ramracheya et al., 2016). PYY is able to decrease food intake and consequently weight gain, effects that are primarily mediated by Y2 receptors of the hypothalamic arcuate nucleus (ARC) (Holzer and Farzi, 2018). In addition, activation of peripheral Y2 receptors, for which PYY is a high-affinity agonist, improves glucose tolerance by increasing GLP-1 levels (Chandarana et al., 2013) although the role of peripheral Y2 receptors in diabetes appears to be complex and to depend on dietary and stress-related circumstances (Shi et al., 2011; Ailanen et al., 2018). It is of particular note that the effect of Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB) surgery to achieve remission of type 2 diabetes, which takes place independently of weight loss, is mediated by PYY (Ramracheya et al., 2016). RYGB surgery increases postprandial PYY levels and insulin secretion (Jacobsen et al., 2012) but the mechanisms whereby RYGB facilitates PYY secretion are still open to analysis. Changes in the gut microbiota composition are very likely to contribute (Federico et al., 2016), given that the gut microbiota stimulates PYY release through the production of SCFAs but is also able to directly induce PYY secretion (Breton et al., 2016). The mechanism through which PYY affects insulin secretion likewise awaits to be investigated, but increases in islet number and size are likely to play a role (Sam et al., 2012). Besides using GLP-1 and PYY as mediators, SCFAs may have a direct effect on pancreatic function. A recent study demonstrated that inulin-propionate ester, which delivers the SCFA propionate to the colon, improves β -cell function independently of GLP-1, an action in which a direct effect of propionate in potentiating insulin release and inhibiting β -cell apoptosis is involved (Pingitore et al., 2017).

As referred to above, SCFAs are multi-target hormones of the intestinal microbiota and can modify the activity of a variety of cells of the gastrointestinal, endocrine, metabolic, immune and nervous systems. The expression of FFARs by these cells enables SCFAs to exert a wide range of beneficial metabolic effects that are at least in part mediated by GLP-1 and PYY, although other SCFA-operated transduction mechanisms may also be involved in the interaction between microbiota and diabetes. It is likely that in this context the ability of SCFAs to strengthen the intestinal mucosal barrier and to exert an anti-inflammatory action on the mucosal immune system is likewise of

particular relevance (Winer et al., 2016). In addition, SCFAs are able to promote the development and physiological function of the BBB and cerebral microglia (Braniste et al., 2014; Erny et al., 2015), which could be mechanisms through which SCFAs exert beneficial effects on brain function and mood. In this regard, especially butyrate, which is able to act as a histone deacetylase inhibitor and thereby to induce epigenetic changes, has been demonstrated to exert anti-depressant effects and increase the central expression of neurotrophic factors (Schroeder et al., 2007; Valvassori et al., 2014). Altogether these results suggest that SCFAs may play an important role in diabetes-brain interaction although their implication in this relationship has not yet been systematically explored.

4.3. Endogenous and bacterial tryptophan metabolites as links in diabetes-brain interaction

Tryptophan (Trp) is an essential amino acid provided by the diet. Within the gut, Trp is metabolized by the intestinal mucosa, but also by enzymes of the intestinal microbiota that metabolizes 4–6% of ingested Trp (Galligan, 2018). While kynurenines, serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine, 5-HT) and melatonin represent endogenous Trp metabolites, the bacterial Trp metabolites include indole, indolic acid, skatole, and tryptamine (Gao et al., 2018). Up to 95% of Trp absorbed by the gut is metabolized along the kynurenine pathway, with tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase (TDO) in the liver and indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO) in extrahepatic tissues being the two rate-limiting enzymes regulating this process (Gao et al., 2018). Importantly, pro-inflammatory cytokines activate IDO and increase the production of kynurenine, which has been proposed to be a key mediator of the anhedonic and anxiety-like behaviour evoked by immune activation, given that kynurenine affects a number of central neurotransmitter systems (O'Connor et al., 2009; Schwarcz et al., 2012). An enhanced activity of the kynurenine pathway has also been associated with diabetes in a case-cohort study, in which kynurenine levels were positively correlated with body mass index and insulin resistance (Favennec et al., 2015).

Although Trp metabolites can target various receptors, the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) has emerged as a particularly crucial mediator of some of the effects of Trp metabolites (Lee et al., 2017). Given that kynurenine is an AhR agonist and mice deficient in IDO1 or AhR are protected from diet-induced obesity, it has been hypothesized that kynurenine signalling through AhR is involved in the pathophysiology of this disease (Moyer et al., 2016). In addition, a case-control study including 83 subjects with type 2 diabetes showed that serum AhR ligand activities are enhanced in the diabetic subjects and correlate with insulin resistance (Roh et al., 2015). Although the AhR ligands associated with insulin resistance await to be identified, the AhR has been proposed to constitute an important signalling pathway between the gut microbiota and host, given that the gut microbiota converts Trp to AhR agonists such as indole, indole-3-propionic acid (IPA), indole-3-acetate, and tryptamine (Jin et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2017).

In contrast to the primarily disadvantageous effects of kynurenines, bacterial Trp metabolites exert rather beneficial actions that are also in part mediated by AhR. For instance, they can strengthen the intestinal barrier and mitigate inflammatory processes (Rothhammer et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2018). Among the microbiota-derived Trp metabolites it is especially IPA which is attributed a favourable activity profile as, for instance, IPA is able to diminish the HFD-induced increase in gut permeability (Jennis et al., 2018). Emerging evidence also points to beneficial effects of IPA in obese and diabetic patients. Thus, IPA levels are lowered in obese subjects and rise following RYGB surgery (Jennis et al., 2018) and, as a Finnish study has shown, high serum levels of IPA are associated with a diminished risk of developing type 2 diabetes (de Mello et al., 2017). In addition, higher IPA levels were found to be associated with higher intake of total fibre, mainly originating from whole grain cereals, which attests to the ability of dietary fibre to

promote beneficial microbiota-related functions (de Mello et al., 2017). Consistently with their positive effect on intestinal immune homeostasis, bacterial Trp metabolites have also been demonstrated to blunt inflammatory processes in the central nervous system through a mechanism involving AhR on astrocytes (Rothhammer et al., 2016). The influence of Trp metabolites on the microglia, however, is more complex, as AhR ligands can mediate both pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory effects in this cellular system (Lee et al., 2017).

Bacterial Trp metabolites other than IPA have less extensively been studied but are also likely to have an impact on diabetes-brain interaction. This is exemplified by indole, which has been demonstrated to increase GLP-1 release from enteroendocrine L-cells of the intestinal epithelium during short exposures, but inhibit GLP-1 secretion after prolonged exposures (Chimerel et al., 2014). These opposite effects are mediated by inhibition of voltage-gated K⁺ channels, which induce GLP-1 secretion, while inhibition of NADH dehydrogenase and reduced ATP production are responsible for the reduction of GLP-1 release (Chimerel et al., 2014). This example is representative of the complex actions which endogenous and microbiota-derived Trp metabolites have on host physiology, including both beneficial and adverse effects that await to be dissected in more detail in their relevance to diabetes and mental illness. It is obvious, however, that bacteria-generated Trp metabolites, like SCFAs, represent important messengers that signal from the gut microbiota to the endocrine and metabolic systems involved in diabetes and, together with endogenous Trp metabolites, have an impact on brain function and behaviour. It should not go unnoticed here that the endogenous kynurenine pathway determines the fraction of Trp that is available for serotonin synthesis. Serotonin is a major signalling molecule both in the enteric and central nervous systems, whose important role in the microbiota-gut-brain axis has been reviewed elsewhere (O'Mahony et al., 2015).

4.4. Microbiota-derived immune stimulants as links in the co-morbidity of diabetes and depression

Inflammatory processes arising from the gut microbiota have been proposed as one of the major factors promoting diabetes (Cani et al., 2008). Especially, increased absorption of the bacterial cell wall component lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from the gut has been demonstrated to trigger inflammatory processes associated with diabetes (Cani et al., 2007). Increased translocation of LPS across the intestinal wall is thought to occur via incorporation of LPS into chylomicrons or through increased permeability of the intestinal mucosal barrier, especially in response to HFD (Ghoshal et al., 2009). HFD-induced gut barrier dysfunction can arise from a change in the gut microbiota composition or a change in endogenous factors that modify intestinal permeability, such as GLP-2 (Cani et al., 2009) and the endocannabinoid system (Muccioli et al., 2010).

LPS is known to stimulate Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4), which induces the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and reactive oxygen species in liver, adipose tissue, and skeletal muscle, these factors interfering with the normal metabolism of the tissue and thus establishing the metabolic effects of LPS (Boutagy et al., 2016). Apart from these metabolic effects, increased circulating levels of LPS (endotoxaemia) induce accumulation of macrophages in white adipose tissue, another process associated with diabetes (Caesar et al., 2012).

It is important to consider that LPS is not the only MAMP/PAMP that contributes to diabetes. The microbiota-induced impairment of glucose and insulin tolerance in mice, for instance, is thought to take place independently of LPS (Caesar et al., 2012). Increased gut permeability enhances the translocation of many bacterial components other than LPS, such as bacterial peptidoglycan fragments activating nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing proteins 1 and 2 (NOD1 and NOD2) which are potentially involved in metabolic inflammation and insulin resistance (Chan et al., 2017). Circulating activators of NOD1 have recently been demonstrated to increase in

response to HFD and to be crucial for diet-induced glucose and insulin intolerance (Chan et al., 2017). Mechanistically, NOD1 promotes the pro-inflammatory polarization of adipose tissue macrophages and increases the production of the neutrophil chemoattractant CXCL1, leading to neutrophil infiltration of adipose tissue (Chan et al., 2017). It is particularly noteworthy that the NOD2 activator muramyl dipeptide (MDP) has been demonstrated to exert effects opposite to that of NOD1 activators, ameliorating insulin resistance and adipose tissue inflammation in obese mice without inducing weight loss (Cavallari et al., 2017). The beneficial effects of MDP are mediated by the transcription factor interferon regulatory factor 4 (Cavallari et al., 2017). These findings indicate that bacterial immune activators do not in general promote insulin resistance. The mechanisms through which inflammatory signals impair insulin receptor sensitivity include an increase in suppressor of cytokine signalling (SOCS) proteins, impaired tyrosine phosphorylation of the insulin receptor and mitigated phosphorylation of insulin receptor substrate proteins (Ueki et al., 2004).

LPS and other microbiota-derived immune stimulants have been extensively studied in their effect on brain and behaviour as reviewed elsewhere (Holzer et al., 2017). By inducing the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines and affecting various signalling systems in the brain, peripheral LPS administration to rodents causes a behavioural syndrome termed sickness behaviour, which may be followed by a period of depression-like behaviour. Other immune stimulants such as NOD1 and NOD2 activators fail to induce pro-inflammatory cytokines on their own but increase cytokine induction and sickness behaviour when administered in combination with LPS (Farzi et al., 2015b). Immune activation and inflammatory processes have long been proposed to be an aetiological factor in the development of mood disorders, encompassed in the cytokine hypothesis of depression (Holzer et al., 2017). Inflammatory processes are also very likely a mechanistic link in the co-morbidity of diabetes and depression (Stuart and Baune, 2012), given that inflammation is associated with both diabetes and depression (Capuron et al., 2017). The associations between diabetes, obesity, stress and mental illness are discussed in detail in section 3 of this article. Similarly to what has been demonstrated for diabetes, inflammatory processes induced by a dysbiotic microbiome have been proposed to induce depressive disorders (Kelly et al., 2016). Thus, faecal microbiota transfer from depressed patients to microbiota-depleted rats is able to induce anhedonia, a characteristic feature of depression, and anxiety-like behaviour in the recipient animals (Kelly et al., 2016). These behavioural changes are paralleled by increased plasma levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines and changes in Trp metabolism (Kelly et al., 2016).

4.5. The endocannabinoid system in microbiota, diabetes and brain coupling

Endocannabinoids are arachidonic acid-derived neuroactive signalling lipids affecting metabolism and appetite through activation of the principal cannabinoid receptors cannabinoid receptor 1 (CB1) and cannabinoid receptor 2 (CB2) as well as other receptors including GPR119 (Cani et al., 2016). A relationship between the endocannabinoid system and metabolic disorders has long been envisaged, and obesity is in general associated with increased endocannabinoid levels in plasma and adipose tissue (Engeli et al., 2005). Apart from its peripheral expression, the CB1 receptor is also widely distributed in the central nervous system where it modulates a plethora of behavioural functions (Busquets-Garcia et al., 2018). Thus, a first-generation CB1 receptor antagonist, rimonabant, was marketed in 2006 as it showed promising effects such as reduction of food intake, body weight and waist circumference (Van Gaal et al., 2005). However, due to severe neuropsychiatric adverse effects including depression and suicide, rimonabant had to be withdrawn from the market (Christensen et al., 2007).

The best studied endocannabinoids are N-

arachidonylethanolamine (AEA, or anandamide) and 2-arachidonylglycerol (2-AG), although other members of the endocannabinoid system likewise exist (Cani et al., 2016). Muccioli et al. (2010) proposed for the first time that the endocannabinoid system could be a link between the gut microbiota and adipogenesis. Specifically, they demonstrated that changing the gut microbiota of obese ob/ob mice by prebiotics decreases adiposity as well as CB1 mRNA expression and AEA levels in adipose tissue. In contrast, stimulation of the endocannabinoid system by the non-selective cannabinoid receptor agonist HU-210 induces adipogenesis in lean mice and increases plasma LPS levels. Importantly, they further demonstrated that the endocannabinoid-induced increase of gut permeability and circulating endotoxin levels in response to HFD is mediated through CB1 receptors (Muccioli et al., 2010).

A subsequent study from the same group showed that feeding of obese and type 2 diabetic mice with a prebiotic normalizes the otherwise decreased abundance of the mucin-degrading bacterium *Akkermansia muciniphila* (Everard et al., 2013). Interestingly, administration of *Akkermansia muciniphila* reverses HFD-induced fat mass gain, metabolic endotoxaemia and insulin resistance, increases the intestinal levels of the endocannabinoid 2-AG and restores gut barrier function. Gut mucosal permeability appears to be under particular control by the endocannabinoid system, and it has been proposed that various endocannabinoids have differential effects on the mucosal gut barrier (Cani et al., 2016). Thus, the endocannabinoid AEA appears to act as a “gate opener”, increasing gut permeability, whereas other cannabinoid receptor ligands including 2-AG act as “gate keepers” (Cani et al., 2016).

Emerging evidence indicates that in these tasks endocannabinoids may be joined by cannabinoid receptor ligands of bacterial origin. A recent study has disclosed that gut bacteria are in fact capable of producing metabolites mimicking endocannabinoids, especially bacterial ligands of the endocannabinoid receptor GPR119 (Cohen et al., 2017). While these studies show that the gut microbiota is able to affect cannabinoid signalling in multiple ways and thereby impact on diabetes, endocannabinoids have also been demonstrated to affect gut microbiota composition (Geurts et al., 2015). Specifically, deletion of the endocannabinoid synthesizing enzyme, NAPE-PLD, in adipocytes induces gut dysbiosis, which leads to enhanced body weight gain and fat mass weight (Geurts et al., 2015). These findings attest to a bidirectional communication between the gut microbiota and endocannabinoids in the context of diabetes. In view of the extensive expression of CB1 receptors in the brain it awaits to be elucidated in which way cannabinoid receptor ligands originating from gut microbiota and host tissue impact on diabetes-related disturbances of brain function.

4.6. Neuropeptide Y (NPY)

NPY is one of the most abundant neuropeptides in the brain, and there is ample evidence that this neuropeptide could play a particular role in diabetes-associated mental disturbances because its expression is altered both by gut dysbiosis and obesity, and the peptide is a major regulator of food intake, stress resilience and emotional-affective behaviour (Holzer, 2016; Reichmann and Holzer, 2016). Specifically, the transcription of the NPY gene in the hypothalamus (Morris et al., 2008) and hippocampus (Hassan et al., 2018) is suppressed in response to diet-induced obesity. The changes of NPY expression in the hypothalamus reflect a role of NPY in metabolic homeostasis and autonomic regulation, whereas those in the hippocampus hint at a role of the neuropeptide in emotional-affective as well as cognitive processes. Experimental diabetes has likewise an impact on cerebral NPY, given that spontaneously diabetic rats and rats with streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetes exhibit increased expression of NPY in the ARC and paraventricular nucleus (PVN) of the hypothalamus, a change that is suppressed by insulin treatment (Abe et al., 1991; Sipols et al., 1995; Fu et al., 2002). Similarly, NPY expression is elevated in the ARC and PVN

of ob/ob mice, excessively obese mice due to a genetic leptin deficiency (Schwartz et al., 1996). Intraperitoneal injection of recombinant leptin downregulates NPY expression in the ARC of ob/ob mice, but not db/db mice (mice with a genetically defect leptin receptor), which indicates that this effect is leptin receptor-dependent (Schwartz et al., 1996).

In addition to its orexigenic effect, NPY may also play a role in the development and progression of diabetes and some associated complications such as atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (Sun et al., 2017). These implications appear to a significant extent be related to peripheral actions of NPY, including inhibition of insulin secretion and a variety of vascular effects. It must not go unnoticed in this context that, apart from its occurrence in cerebral neurons, NPY is also expressed in noradrenergic neurons of the sympathetic nervous system. Experiments manipulating NPY expression specifically in the noradrenergic system have demonstrated that catecholaminergic NPY signalling is critical in mediating diet- and chronic stress-induced fat gain via effects on diet-induced thermogenesis and stress-induced increases in corticosterone levels and lipogenic capacity (Zhang et al., 2014). Mice overexpressing NPY in the sympathetic noradrenergic system have an enhanced white adipose tissue mass, display a metabolic-syndrome-like phenotype, and are more vulnerable to develop diabetes in response to a high caloric diet combined with a low dose STZ (Ruohonen et al., 2008; Ailanen et al., 2017). Circulating NPY is increased in mice fed with a HFD (Hassan et al., 2018) and has been reported to be elevated in obese women (Baranowska et al., 1997). Increased peripheral NPY appears to contribute to the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis through a variety of mechanisms: vasoconstriction, promotion of vascular endothelial dysfunction, formation of foam cells, proliferation of vascular smooth muscle cells, and activation and aggregation of platelets (Zhu et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2017).

The central NPY system is sensitive to alterations in the composition of the intestinal microbiota as well as to peripheral immune stimulation. Treatment of mice with a mix of antibiotics, that are minimally absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract and do not enter the brain, leads to a specific increment of NPY mRNA expression in the amygdala and hypothalamus (Fröhlich et al., 2016). This finding is in keeping with data from germ-free mice in which an increase in the expression of NPY and AgrP in the hypothalamus has been observed (Schéle et al., 2013). In addition, antibiotic-induced gut dysbiosis impacts on the cerebral transcription of NPY receptors of the Y1, Y2 and Y5 type in distinct areas of the mouse brain including the hypothalamus, amygdala, and hippocampus (Fröhlich et al., 2016). The downregulation of Y2 receptors in the hippocampus of antibiotic-treated mice has been proposed to play a role in the cognitive deficit found in these animals (Fröhlich et al., 2016; Holzer, 2016). Both the peripheral and cerebral NPY systems are also sensitive to intestinal inflammation, as experimental colitis leads to an increase of both circulating and hypothalamic NPY (Hassan et al., 2014). In the brain, NPY is thought to protect against distinct functional disturbances in response to immune challenge and in this way to prevent the development of mental disease (Farzi et al., 2015a). Specifically, NPY is involved in the regulation of the microglia which is increasingly recognized to play a crucial role in the development of psychiatric disorders such as major depression (Yirmiya et al., 2015) and in the neuroinflammatory processes induced by an obesogenic diet (Valdearcos et al., 2014). In the microglia, NPY seems to play a protective role as it inhibits LPS-induced activation of microglial cells and the concomitant expression of neuroinflammation-relevant factors (Carniglia et al., 2017).

NPY is just one of many neuropeptides, neurotransmitters and other neuromediator systems in the brain that are targeted by the gut microbiota and altered by changes in the microbiota composition (Holzer, 2016; Luczynski et al., 2016). Instead of a comprehensive coverage of this mediator network, we focus here on NPY as a model neuropeptide that plays multiple physiological and pathophysiological roles in the brain, with a particular involvement in stress-related emotional-affective disorders. However, it must not go unnoticed in this regard that

NPY interacts with many other signalling molecules and systems, notably corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF, also known as corticotropin-releasing hormone). CRF is an essential mediator of the HPA axis and the stress response mediated by this system. In keeping with this function, CRF is thought to participate in the pathophysiology of depression and mood disorders (Naughton et al., 2014).

Although conclusive evidence for an involvement of NPY in the link between diabetes and brain dysfunction has not yet been obtained, the findings discussed here make a strong case that this neuropeptide is involved. The analysis of NPY's pathophysiological implications is complicated by the diverse roles this neuropeptide and its receptors play in the periphery and brain (Farzi et al., 2015a) and by the lack of powerful pharmacological tools to dissect the roles of the multiple NPY receptors involved in the actions of NPY. Despite these drawbacks, the available information indicates that both the peripheral and central NPY systems react to food intake and type of diet, changes in the composition of the intestinal microbiome, peripheral inflammation, stress, and other conditions relevant to obesity and diabetes. It awaits to be explored whether the dynamic changes in the cerebral NPY system in metabolic and inflammatory disease represent attempts to counter-regulate the adverse effects of these conditions on the brain or reflect the pathological changes in brain function associated with diabetes.

4.7. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF)

BDNF is a member of the family of neurotrophins and an essential factor for the growth and survival of a variety of neurons in the central nervous system, especially in the hippocampus and frontal cortex. BDNF and its receptors are widely distributed in the brain and in their neuronal actions are relevant to several physiological functions including learning, memory and neurogenesis (Lu et al., 2014). There is also extensive experimental and clinical evidence that attributes BDNF a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of major depression. Thus, the levels of this neurotrophic factor in the plasma as well as in post-mortem brain samples of depressed patients are reduced, as is the expression of BDNF in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex of stress-induced animal models of depression (Castrén and Kojima, 2017). Antidepressant treatment can restore the deficient plasma and brain levels of BDNF and stimulate neurogenesis in the dentate gyrus of the hippocampus, a finding that backs the neurogenesis theory of depression (Schoenfeld and Cameron, 2015; Castrén and Kojima, 2017).

In rodents, diet-induced obesity and diabetes are associated with reduced neurogenesis in the dentate gyrus as well as reduced expression of BDNF in the hippocampus (Molteni et al., 2004; Park et al., 2010; Ho et al., 2013; Dorsemans et al., 2017). Noteworthy, diet restriction has the opposite effect, increasing the expression of hippocampal BDNF in the hippocampus and promoting the survival of newly generated neurons while the proliferation of neuronal stem cells is not significantly affected (Lee et al., 2002). However, the diet-related regulation of BDNF in the brain is region-specific and, unlike in the hippocampus, its expression in the mouse nucleus accumbens, ventral tegmental area, and dorsolateral striatum is increased by HFD (Sharma and Fulton, 2013). The enhanced BDNF levels in the nucleus accumbens and dorsolateral striatum of rodents correlate positively with the development of depression-like behaviour (Sharma and Fulton, 2013; Castrén and Kojima, 2017). In humans, the study of BDNF in diabetic subjects has yielded inconsistent results as both an increase (Suwa et al., 2006) as well as a decrease (Krabbe et al., 2007; Wang and He, 2015) of the plasma levels of BDNF in patients with type 2 diabetes have been reported. It is worth noting in this context that BDNF can influence appetite and sympathetic discharge, which in turn has an impact on blood glucose levels and adiposity (Marchelek-Myśliwiec et al., 2013).

Although direct evidence for a role of BDNF in the link between diabetes and mental illness has not yet been established, its regulation by diabetes-related conditions and its major involvement in mental illness (Schoenfeld and Cameron, 2015) make BDNF an important

serious candidate link. This argument is further supported by consistent findings that the cerebral regulation of BDNF expression is under the influence of the gut microbiota. For example, infection of mice with the intestinal parasite *Trichuris muris* leads to a reduction of hippocampal BDNF gene expression, an effect that can be reversed by the probiotic *Bifidobacterium longum* NCC3001 (Bercik et al., 2010). Experimentally induced colitis likewise lowers BDNF mRNA levels in the hippocampus (Hassan et al., 2014) as does antibiotic-induced depletion of the gut microbiome (Fröhlich et al., 2016) although the pertinent findings reported in the literature are in part inconsistent (Holzer, 2016).

4.8. γ -Amino butyric acid (GABA)

GABA is the main inhibitory neurotransmitter in the brain, and in consideration of its broad role in cerebral function it would seem unlikely that GABA represents a particular link between diabetes and mental illness. There is, however, evidence that distinct units of the cerebral GABA system are targeted by signals from the gut microbiota as well as by obesity- and diabetes-related signals. In addition, GABAergic signalling is well established to play an important role in the pathophysiology of anxiety and mood disorders. Like depressed patients who have lowered GABA levels in the occipital and prefrontal cortex (Luscher et al., 2011), rats with a stress-evoked depression-like phenotype present with reduced GABA levels in the prefrontal cortex (Shalaby and Kamal, 2009; Ma et al., 2016; Banasr et al., 2017). Importantly, both the cortical GABA deficiency and depression-like behaviour induced by chronic mild stress are reversed by the antidepressant escitalopram (Shalaby and Kamal, 2009).

It is particularly worth noting that both an obesogenic diet and diabetes impact on the cerebral GABA system. We have shown that the depression-like behaviour induced by HFD in mice is also associated with a diminished concentration of GABA in the prefrontal cortex (Hassan et al., 2018), a finding that is in keeping with a reduction of GABA levels in the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus of HFD-fed rats (Sandoval-Salazar et al., 2016). Moreover, STZ-induced diabetes results in diminished GABA levels in the striatum of rats, a change that is associated with behavioural signs of depression (Gomez et al., 2003). In line with this experimental observation, a small study of diabetic neuropathy patients revealed a deficiency of GABA in the posterior insula (Petrou et al., 2012). However, it cannot go unnoticed that enhanced brain levels of GABA have also been reported in patients suffering from type 2 diabetes (van Bussel et al., 2016). Insulin resistance has an impact on the brain, and there is abundant evidence that insulin regulates various brain functions including the GABA system, an issue that is discussed in more detail by J.C. Brüning and colleagues in their article of this special issue.

Another GABAergic link between diabetes and mental illness may be found in the gut microbiota-brain axis. Several members of the commensal gut microbiome including *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* strains are themselves able to produce GABA (Barrett et al., 2012; Yunes et al., 2016). Prolonged administration of a GABA-producing *Lactobacillus* strain to STZ-treated diabetic rats has been reported to reduce the diabetes-associated hyperglycaemia (Marques et al., 2016), while administration of a GABA-producing *Bifidobacterium* strain is able to modulate sensory neuron activity in the rat intestine, reducing visceral hypersensitivity (Pokusaeva et al., 2017). Furthermore, a disturbance of the gut microbial community has an appreciable impact on the cerebral GABA system along with behavioural perturbations. Thus, antibiotic-induced gut dysbiosis in juvenile rats has been found to induce depression-like behaviour and cognitive impairment persisting into adulthood, these changes being associated with reduced expression of GABA_A receptor $\alpha 5$ and δ subunits in the hippocampus (Liang et al., 2017). Vice versa, the administration of a probiotic, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* (JB-1), to BALB/c mice is able to increase the cerebral concentration of GABA (Janik et al., 2016) along with changes in GABA_A and GABA_B receptor expression in specific brain regions, accompanied

by a reduction of anxiety and depression-related behaviour (Bravo et al., 2011). Taken together, these findings attest to a distinct relationship between intestinal microbiota, obesity, diabetes and cerebral GABA system, a relationship that may have a bearing on diabetes-related mood disorders.

5. Diet-related interventions to target the interaction between diabetes and mood disorders

Given the evidence that quality and caloric content of the diet have a huge impact on diabetes as well as on the microbiota-gut-brain axis, adjustment of nutritional composition and eating habits have been extensively studied for their ability to ameliorate diabetes, obesity and mental health. Three approaches are most widely used: (i) time-restricted eating during each day resulting in a diminution of the overall daily calorie intake, (ii) intermittent fasting involving alternate day fasting with calorie-restricted food intake or no food intake at all every other day, and (iii) calorie restriction by limiting the daily calorie intake to, e.g., 70% of the ad libitum ratio (Redman et al., 2008; Klempel et al., 2012; Eshghinia and Mohammadzadeh, 2013; Hussin et al., 2013; Varady et al., 2013; Horne et al., 2015). In humans, intermittent fasting with energy intake restriction every other day is of comparable efficacy in reducing body weight and improving insulin sensitivity as restriction of total daily calorie intake (Harvie et al., 2011; Barnosky et al., 2014). These clinical findings are in keeping with experimental studies in which mice fed a diet high in sugar and fat content for 12 weeks gained significantly less weight if their access to food was restricted to 9 h per day compared to mice with ad libitum access to the same food (Chaix et al., 2014). The reduced weight gain was observed despite the fact that both groups of mice ingested the same overall amount of daily calories. Furthermore, time-restricted access to a HFD did not only attenuate total body mass gain, but also reduced fasting insulin levels (Hatori et al., 2012; Chaix et al., 2014). However, the insulin-regulating effect of restricted feeding was absent when the HFD was enriched with a high sucrose content (Hatori et al., 2012; Chaix et al., 2014).

Diet-related interventions influence the gut microbiome composition although there are some inconsistencies in the effects reported (Zheng et al., 2018). A switch to time-restricted feeding in mice with HFD-induced obesity restores key components of the gut microbiota and promotes the occurrence of Ruminococcaceae species that are thought to protect against obesity (Zarrinpar et al., 2014). Other studies found that calorie restriction in rodents on both low-fat diet or HFD significantly changes the overall structure of the gut microbiota in an age-dependent manner, with an expansion of *Bifidobacterium* spp. and *Lactobacillus* spp. (Zhang et al., 2013; Fraumene et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Antibiotic-induced depletion of the gut microbiota renders mice resistant to the loss of body weight caused by calorie reduction (Wang et al., 2018). This finding and the observation that gut microbiota transfer from calorie-restricted mice prevents HFD-induced obesity indicates that the gut microbiota mediates the anti-obesity effect of calorie restriction (Wang et al., 2018). A restricted intake of calories by humans (mean daily intake of 1700 kcal for one year) has likewise been found to align the gut microbiome to that found in lean subjects, resulting in a reduction of the overall Firmicutes:Bacteroidetes ratio (Ruiz et al., 2017).

Intermittent fasting, another intervention that impacts on the gut microbiome, stimulates browning of white adipose tissue and ameliorates diabetes (Li et al., 2017). Specifically, intermittent fasting shifts the gut microbiota composition to produce increased levels of the fermentation products acetate and lactate and upregulates monocarboxylate transporter 1 expression in beige cells. The metabolic and anti-obesity effects of intermittent fasting in HFD-fed mice depend on the gut microbiota because they are absent in microbiota-depleted mice (Li et al., 2017). In addition, gut microbiota transfer from mice subjected to intermittent fasting to microbiota-depleted mice activates adipose tissue browning and improves metabolic homeostasis (Li et al.,

2017). Intermittent fasting for 15 h daily also prevents the development of diabetes in STZ-treated rats fed either a hypercaloric or control diet (Belkacemi et al., 2010). Further studies indicate that the ability of intermittent fasting to prevent STZ-induced diabetes is probably due to protection of pancreatic β -cells via an increase of cellular stress resistance (Belkacemi et al., 2012; Mattson et al., 2017). Moreover, the beneficial effects of food and calorie restriction in diabetes are thought to involve the induction of autophagy (Mattson et al., 2017) which is critical for lipid metabolism and triglyceride breakdown and helps maintaining cellular tissue functionality by elimination of misfolded proteins and cell debris (Singh et al., 2009; Muriach et al., 2014).

Although a direct impact of time- and calorie-restricted food intake on diabetes-related brain dysfunction has been little explored, such a relationship is very likely to exist in view of the mechanisms governing the comorbidity of diabetes and mental disorders as reviewed here. Alternate day fasting without food every other day initiates adaptive processes in the rodent brain, including upregulation of BDNF, which is associated with increases in synaptic plasticity and cognitive function as well as neuroprotection (Lee et al., 2002; Rothman et al., 2012). BDNF may play a similar role in humans as (i) BDNF levels in plasma of type 2 diabetes as well as obese patients are significantly decreased compared to the respective healthy controls, and (ii) plasma levels of BDNF are inversely related to fasting plasma glucose levels, which suggests a potential role of BDNF in glucose homeostasis and diabetes (Krabbe et al., 2007).

Experimentally induced impairment of cognitive function is a pathology that appears to particularly benefit from a change in dieting schedule. Both intermittent fasting and 40% calorie restriction have been reported to alleviate cognitive deficits in a transgenic mouse model of Alzheimer's disease, although intermittent fasting does not reduce amyloid- β peptide accumulation (Halagappa et al., 2007). This finding is of particular interest, given that the incidence of Alzheimer's disease is increased in diabetic patients (for a review see (Jayaraman and Pike, 2014)). Up-regulated BDNF expression due to fasting could also be of importance in this condition, since BDNF was shown to prevent amyloid- β -dependent impairment of long-term potentiation in entorhinal cortex slices. This effect was linked to a TrkB (BDNF) receptor-mediated inhibition of p38 MAP kinase phosphorylation, which is thought to result in synaptic dysfunction and impairment of long-term potentiation (Criscuolo et al., 2015).

Other mechanisms that could play a role in diet-induced beneficial effects relate to the moderate stress that occurs in rodents when access to food is restricted. Activation of the HPA axis is mirrored by an elevated expression of heat-shock proteins and reduced expression of glucocorticoid receptors in the hippocampus and cortex, which under this condition of mild stress may reflect a neuroprotective action enhancing synaptic plasticity (Aly et al., 1994; Lee et al., 2000). Low-grade or overt inflammation is a further factor that is of considerable relevance to diabetes, obesity and mental health, and it is important to note that inflammation can be attenuated by food restriction. Thus, the expression patterns of pro-inflammatory cytokines including tumour necrosis factor- α and interleukin-1 β in the brown adipose tissue are down-regulated in mice subjected to a time-restricted feeding regimen involving a high-fat or high-fat plus high-sugar diet relative to ad libitum fed controls (Chaix et al., 2014). This experimental finding has a parallel in humans, given that fasting during the month of Ramadan reduces the circulating levels of interleukin-1 β and tumour necrosis factor- α , these effects vanishing after the end of Ramadan (Faris et al., 2012).

While the beneficial effects of calorie restriction and fasting discussed here seem to be persuasive, it should not go unnoticed that these dieting regimens have some downsides, especially when applied in the long-term. For instance, non-obese humans subjected to intermittent fasting (no food every other day) experience difficulties in complying with the dieting schedule for a prolonged period of time because the feeling of hunger on the fasting days does not decrease during a period

of 3 weeks (Heilbronn et al., 2005). In addition, non-obese human volunteers do not seem to be able to maintain their body weight over a 3-week period of intermittent fasting, while rodent studies hold that no overall loss of weight occurs (Heilbronn et al., 2005). Unfavourable effects, however, may also occur in animal models of long-term feeding restriction. Thus, intermittently fasted Sprague-Dawley rats, a strain prone to develop obesity, presented with a similar abdominal adipose tissue accumulation as ad libitum fed control animals following 32 weeks of dietary intervention, although the overall body weight was lower in the fasted group (Cerqueira et al., 2011). Furthermore, intermittent fasting for 32, but not 4, weeks promoted glucose intolerance and led to insulin receptor inactivation in both intra-abdominal adipose tissue and skeletal muscle. Notably, these adverse effects of long-term intermittent fasting were not observed in a simultaneously studied group of rats subjected to 40% calorie restriction (Cerqueira et al., 2011). Another study found that alternate day fasting over 3 months caused up-regulated expression of pro-inflammatory markers and insulin resistance in diabetes-prone hypercholesterolaemic LDL-receptor knockout mice (Dorigheo et al., 2014). Taken together, these studies indicate that the intermittent fasting schedule is limited by a number of unfavourable long-term effects that cast doubt on the therapeutic usefulness of this approach.

6. Conclusions

Obesity and type 2 diabetes have become a global epidemic and are still on the rise, which claims an increasing share of the clinical, social and economic health burden (Cuschieri et al., 2016). The reciprocal relationship between diabetes and neuropsychiatric disease, especially depression, aggravates this health issue and calls for a mechanistic analysis of the co-morbidity to guide preventive and therapeutic strategies. The framework we have presented in this review is shaped by our knowledge of the microbiota-gut-brain axis, as the communication links operating in gut-brain communication seem to have a definite bearing on the interaction between unhealthy eating habits, obesity, diabetes and brain dysfunction. For the time being, factors derived from the gut microbiota appear to orchestrate a number of these interactions, but the fascination with this newly discovered network should not blur the fact that our understanding of the diabetes-brain relationship is still fragmentary. As regards the impact of obesity and diabetes on the brain, there is emerging evidence that these adverse conditions target particular microglial and neuronal circuits in the central nervous system. From a neuropsychiatric point of view, it is equally important to analyse both the molecular and network mechanisms of diabetes-associated mental illness in order to interrupt and manage the reciprocal relationship between diabetes and mood disorders.

Acknowledgements

Work in the authors' laboratory was supported by grant 613979 of the European Commission, Belgium (MyNewGut, www.mynewgut.eu), and the Austrian Science Fund, Austria (FWF grants P23097-B18, P25912-B23, W1241-B18 and an *Erwin Schrödinger Fellowship* to Aitak Farzi). The help of Judith Holzer, MD, in drawing Fig. 1 is greatly appreciated.

References

Abe, M., Saito, M., Ikeda, H., Shimazu, T., 1991. Increased neuropeptide Y content in the arcuate-paraventricular hypothalamic neuronal system in both insulin-dependent and non-insulin-dependent diabetic rats. *Brain Res.* 539, 223–227.

Ailanen, L., Ruohonen, S.T., Vahatalo, L.H., Tuomainen, K., Eerola, K., Salomaki-Myftari, H., Roytta, M., Laiho, A., Ahotupa, M., Gylling, H., et al., 2017. The metabolic syndrome in mice overexpressing neuropeptide Y in noradrenergic neurons. *J. Endocrinol.* 234, 57–72.

Ailanen, L., Vahatalo, L.H., Salomaki-Myftari, H., Makela, S., Orpana, W., Ruohonen, S.T., Savontaus, E., 2018. Peripherally administered Y2-receptor antagonist BIIE0246 prevents diet-induced obesity in mice with excess neuropeptide Y, but enhances

obesity in control mice. *Front. Pharmacol.* 9, 319.

Aly, K.B., Pipkin, J.L., Hinson, W.G., Feuers, R.J., Duffey, P.H., Lyn-Cook, L., Hart, R.W., 1994. Chronic caloric restriction induces stress proteins in the hypothalamus of rats. *Mech. Ageing Dev.* 76, 11–23.

Atlantis, E., Baker, M., 2008. Obesity effects on depression: systematic review of epidemiological studies. *Int. J. Obes. (Lond)* 32, 881–891.

Avila, C., Holloway, A.C., Hahn, M.K., Morrison, K.M., Restivo, M., Anglin, R., Taylor, V.H., 2015. An overview of links between obesity and mental health. *Curr Obes Rep* 4, 303–310.

Bäckhed, F., Manchester, J.K., Semenkovich, C.F., Gordon, J.I., 2007. Mechanisms underlying the resistance to diet-induced obesity in germ-free mice. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 104, 979–984.

Banasr, M., Lepack, A., Fee, C., Duric, V., Maldonado-Aviles, J., DiLeone, R., Sibille, E., Duman, R.S., Sanacora, G., 2017. Characterization of GABAergic marker expression in the chronic unpredictable stress model of depression. *Chronic Stress (Thousand Oaks)* in press.

Baranowska, B., Wasilewska-Dziubinska, E., Radzikowska, M., Plonowski, A., Roguski, K., 1997. Neuropeptide Y, galanin, and leptin release in obese women and in women with anorexia nervosa. *Metab. Clin. Exp.* 46, 1384–1389.

Barnosky, A.R., Hoddy, K.K., Unterman, T.G., Varady, K.A., 2014. Intermittent fasting vs daily calorie restriction for type 2 diabetes prevention: a review of human findings. *Transl. Res.* 164, 302–311.

Barrett, E., Ross, R.P., O'Toole, P.W., Fitzgerald, G.F., Stanton, C., 2012. gamma-Aminobutyric acid production by culturable bacteria from the human intestine. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 113, 411–417.

Belkacemi, L., Selselet-Attou, G., Hupkens, E., Nguidjoe, E., Louchami, K., Sener, A., Malaisse, W.J., 2012. Intermittent fasting modulation of the diabetic syndrome in streptozotocin-injected rats. *Internet J. Endocrinol.* 2012, 962012.

Belkacemi, L., Selselet-Attou, G., Louchami, K., Sener, A., Malaisse, W.J., 2010. Intermittent fasting modulation of the diabetic syndrome in sand rats. II. In vivo investigations. *Int. J. Mol. Med.* 26, 759–765.

Bercik, P., Verdu, E.F., Foster, J.A., Macri, J., Potter, M., Huang, X., Malinowski, P., Jackson, W., Blennerhassett, P., Neufeld, K.A., et al., 2010. Chronic gastrointestinal inflammation induces anxiety-like behavior and alters central nervous system biochemistry in mice. *Gastroenterology* 139, 2102–2112 e2101.

Bindels, L.B., Dewulf, E.M., Delzenne, N.M., 2013. GPR43/FFA2: physiopathological relevance and therapeutic prospects. *Trends Pharmacol. Sci.* 34, 226–232.

Boutagy, N.E., McMillan, R.P., Frisard, M.I., Hulver, M.W., 2016. Metabolic endotoxemia with obesity: is it real and is it relevant? *Biochimie* 124, 11–20.

Braniste, V., Al-Asmakh, M., Kowal, C., Anuar, F., Abbaspour, A., Toth, M., Korecka, A., Bakocevic, N., Ng, L.G., Kundu, P., et al., 2014. The gut microbiota influences blood-brain barrier permeability in mice. *Sci. Transl. Med.* 6, 263ra158.

Bravo, J.A., Forsythe, P., Chew, M.V., Escaravage, E., Savignac, H.M., Dinan, T.G., Bienenstock, J., Cryan, J.F., 2011. Ingestion of *Lactobacillus* strain regulates emotional behavior and central GABA receptor expression in a mouse via the vagus nerve. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 108, 16050–16055.

Breton, J., Tennyson, N., Lucas, N., Francois, M., Legrand, R., Jacquemot, J., Goichon, A., Guerin, C., Peltier, J., Pestel-Caron, M., et al., 2016. Gut commensal *E. coli* proteins activate host satiety pathways following nutrient-induced bacterial growth. *Cell Metabol.* 23, 324–334.

Brown, A.J., Goldsworthy, S.M., Barnes, A.A., Eilert, M.M., Tcheang, L., Daniels, D., Muir, A.I., Wigglesworth, M.J., Kinghorn, I., Fraser, N.J., et al., 2003. The Orphan G protein-coupled receptors GPR41 and GPR43 are activated by propionate and other short chain carboxylic acids. *J. Biol. Chem.* 278, 11312–11319.

Bruce-Keller, A.J., Salbaum, J.M., Luo, M., Blanchard, E.T., Taylor, C.M., Welsh, D.A., Berthoud, H.R., 2015. Obese-type gut microbiota induce neurobehavioral changes in the absence of obesity. *Biol. Psychiatry* 77, 607–615.

Busquets-García, A., Bains, J., Marsicano, G., 2018. CB₁ receptor signaling in the brain: extracting specificity from ubiquity. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 43, 4–20.

Caesar, R., Reigstad, C.S., Bäckhed, H.K., Reinhardt, C., Ketonen, M., Lunden, G.O., Cani, P.D., Bäckhed, F., 2012. Gut-derived lipopolysaccharide augments adipose macrophage accumulation but is not essential for impaired glucose or insulin tolerance in mice. *Gut* 61, 1701–1707.

Cani, P.D., Amar, J., Iglesias, M.A., Poggi, M., Knauf, C., Bastelica, D., Neyrinck, A.M., Fava, F., Tuohy, K.M., Chabo, C., et al., 2007. Metabolic endotoxemia initiates obesity and insulin resistance. *Diabetes* 56, 1761–1772.

Cani, P.D., Bibiloni, R., Knauf, C., Waget, A., Neyrinck, A.M., Delzenne, N.M., Burcelin, R., 2008. Changes in gut microbiota control metabolic endotoxemia-induced inflammation in high-fat diet-induced obesity and diabetes in mice. *Diabetes* 57, 1470–1481.

Cani, P.D., Plovier, H., Van Hul, M., Geurts, L., Delzenne, N.M., Druart, C., Everard, A., 2016. Endocannabinoids – at the crossroads between the gut microbiota and host metabolism. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* 12, 133–143.

Cani, P.D., Possemiers, S., Van de Wiele, T., Guiot, Y., Everard, A., Rottier, O., Geurts, L., Naslain, D., Neyrinck, A., Lambert, D.M., et al., 2009. Changes in gut microbiota control inflammation in obese mice through a mechanism involving GLP-2-driven improvement of gut permeability. *Gut* 58, 1091–1103.

Capuron, L., Lasselien, J., Castanon, N., 2017. Role of adiposity-driven inflammation in depressive morbidity. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 42, 115–128.

Carniglia, L., Ramirez, D., Durand, D., Saba, J., Turati, J., Caruso, C., Scimionelli, T.N., Lasaga, M., 2017. Neuropeptides and microglial activation in inflammation, pain, and neurodegenerative diseases. *Mediat. Inflamm.* 2017, 5048616.

Castrén, E., Kojima, M., 2017. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in mood disorders and antidepressant treatments. *Neurobiol. Dis.* 97, 119–126.

Cavallari, J.F., Fullerton, M.D., Duggan, B.M., Foley, K.P., Denou, E., Smith, B.K., Desjardins, E.M., Henriksbo, B.D., Kim, K.J., Tuinema, B.R., et al., 2017. Muramyl

- dipeptide-based postbiotics mitigate obesity-induced insulin resistance via IRF4. *Cell Metabol.* 25, 1063–1074 e1063.
- Cerqueira, F.M., da Cunha, F.M., Caldeira da Silva, C.C., Chausse, B., Romano, R.L., Garcia, C.C., Colepicolo, P., Medeiros, M.H., Kowaltowski, A.J., 2011. Long-term intermittent feeding, but not caloric restriction, leads to redox imbalance, insulin receptor nitration, and glucose intolerance. *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 51, 1454–1460.
- Chaix, A., Zarrinpar, A., Miu, P., Panda, S., 2014. Time-restricted feeding is a preventative and therapeutic intervention against diverse nutritional challenges. *Cell Metabol.* 20, 991–1005.
- Chan, K.L., Tam, T.H., Boroumand, P., Prescott, D., Costford, S.R., Escalante, N.K., Fine, N., Tu, Y., Robertson, S.J., Prabhakaran, D., et al., 2017. Circulating NOD1 Activators and hematopoietic NOD1 contribute to metabolic inflammation and insulin resistance. *Cell Rep.* 18, 2415–2426.
- Chandarana, K., Gelegen, C., Irvine, E.E., Choudhury, A.I., Amouyal, C., Andreelli, F., Withers, D.J., Batterham, R.L., 2013. Peripheral activation of the Y2-receptor promotes secretion of GLP-1 and improves glucose tolerance. *Mol Metab* 2, 142–152.
- Chandra, R., Hiniker, A., Kuo, Y.M., Nussbaum, R.L., Liddle, R.A., 2017. alpha-Synuclein in gut endocrine cells and its implications for Parkinson's disease. *JCI Insight* 2, e92295.
- Chen, S., Zhang, Q., Dai, G., Hu, J., Zhu, C., Su, L., Wu, X., 2016. Association of depression with pre-diabetes, undiagnosed diabetes, and previously diagnosed diabetes: a meta-analysis. *Endocrine* 53, 35–46.
- Chimerel, C., Emery, E., Summers, D.K., Keyser, U., Gribble, F.M., Reimann, F., 2014. Bacterial metabolite indole modulates incretin secretion from intestinal enteroendocrine L cells. *Cell Rep.* 9, 1202–1208.
- Cholerton, B., Baker, L.D., Craft, S., 2013. Insulin, cognition, and dementia. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 719, 170–179.
- Christensen, R., Kristensen, P.K., Bartels, E.M., Bliddal, H., Astrup, A., 2007. Efficacy and safety of the weight-loss drug rimonabant: a meta-analysis of randomised trials. *Lancet* 370, 1706–1713.
- Cohen, L.J., Esterhazy, D., Kim, S.H., Lemetre, C., Aguilar, R.R., Gordon, E.A., Pickard, A.J., Cross, J.R., Emiliano, A.B., Han, S.M., et al., 2017. Commensal bacteria make GPCR ligands that mimic human signalling molecules. *Nature* 549, 48–53.
- Colle, R., de Laminat, D., Rotenberg, S., Hozer, F., Hardy, P., Verstuyft, C., Fève, B., Corruble, E., 2017. PPAR-γ agonists for the treatment of major depression: a review. *Pharmacopsychiatry* 50, 49–55.
- Craig, A.D., 2002. How do you feel? Interoception: the sense of the physiological condition of the body. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 3, 655–666.
- Criscuolo, C., Fabiani, C., Bonadonna, C., Origlia, N., Domenici, L., 2015. BDNF prevents amyloid-dependent impairment of LTP in the entorhinal cortex by attenuating p38 MAPK phosphorylation. *Neurobiol. Aging* 36, 1303–1309.
- Cuschieri, S., Vassallo, J., Calleja, N., Pace, N., Abela, J., Ali, B.A., Abdullah, F., Zahra, E., Mamo, J., 2016. The diabetes health economic crisis—the size of the crisis in a European island state following a cross-sectional study. *Arch. Public Health* 74, 52.
- Dallman, M.F., 2010. Stress-induced obesity and the emotional nervous system. *Trends Endocrinol. Metabol.* 21, 159–165.
- de Groot, M., Crick, K.A., Long, M., Saha, C., Shubrook, J.H., 2016. Lifetime duration of depressive disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 39, 2174–2181.
- De Hert, M., Correll, C.U., Bobes, J., Cetkovich-Bakmas, M., Cohen, D., Asai, I., Detraux, J., Gautam, S., Moller, H.J., Ndetei, D.M., et al., 2011. Physical illness in patients with severe mental disorders. I. Prevalence, impact of medications and disparities in health care. *World Psychiatr.* 10, 52–77.
- de Mello, V.D., Paananen, J., Lindstrom, J., Lankinen, M.A., Shi, L., Kuusisto, J., Pihlajamaki, J., Auriola, S., Lehtonen, M., Rolandsson, O., et al., 2017. Indolepropionic acid and novel lipid metabolites are associated with a lower risk of type 2 diabetes in the Finnish Diabetes Prevention Study. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 46337.
- den Besten, G., Bleeker, A., Gerding, A., van Eunen, K., Havinga, R., van Dijk, T.H., Oosterveer, M.H., Jonker, J.W., Groen, A.K., Reijngoud, D.J., et al., 2015. Short-chain fatty acids protect against high-fat diet-induced obesity via a PPARγ-dependent switch from lipogenesis to fat oxidation. *Diabetes* 64, 2398–2408.
- Diamant, M., Blaak, E.E., de Vos, W.M., 2011. Do nutrient-gut-microbiota interactions play a role in human obesity, insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes? *Obes. Rev.* 12, 272–281.
- Diz-Chaves, Y., Gil-Lozano, M., Toba, L., Fandino, J., Ogando, H., Gonzalez-Matias, L.C., Mallo, F., 2016. Stressing diabetes? The hidden links between insulinotropic peptides and the HPA axis. *J. Endocrinol.* 230, R77–R94.
- Dorighele, G.G., Rovani, J.C., Luhman, C.J., Paim, B.A., Raposo, H.F., Vercesi, A.E., Oliveira, H.C., 2014. Food restriction by intermittent fasting induces diabetes and obesity and aggravates spontaneous atherosclerosis development in hypercholesterolaemic mice. *Br. J. Nutr.* 111, 979–986.
- Dorseman, A.C., Couret, D., Hoarau, A., Meilhac, O., Lefebvre d'Hellencourt, C., Diotel, N., 2017. Diabetes, adult neurogenesis and brain remodeling: new insights from rodent and zebrafish models. *Neurogenesis (Austin, Tex)* 4, e1281862.
- Duthiel, S., Ota, K.T., Wohleb, E.S., Rasmussen, K., Duman, R.S., 2016. High-fat diet induced anxiety and anhedonia: impact on brain homeostasis and inflammation. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 41, 1874–1887.
- Eaton, W.W., Armenian, H., Gallo, J., Pratt, L., Ford, D.E., 1996. Depression and risk for onset of type II diabetes. A prospective population-based study. *Diabetes Care* 19, 1097–1102.
- Engeli, S., Böhnke, J., Feldpausch, M., Gorzelnik, K., Janke, J., Bätka, S., Pacher, P., Harvey-White, J., Luft, F.C., Sharma, A.M., et al., 2005. Activation of the peripheral endocannabinoid system in human obesity. *Diabetes* 54, 2838–2843.
- Epel, E., Jimenez, S., Brownell, K., Stroud, L., Stoney, C., Niaura, R., 2004. Are stress eaters at risk for the metabolic syndrome? *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1032, 208–210.
- Erny, D., Hrabé de Angelis, A.L., Jaitin, D., Wieghofer, P., Staszewski, O., David, E., Keren-Shaul, H., Mhalkoiv, T., Jakobshagen, K., Buch, T., et al., 2015. Host microbiota constantly control maturation and function of microglia in the CNS. *Nat. Neurosci.* 18, 965–977.
- Eshghinia, S., Mohammadzadeh, F., 2013. The effects of modified alternate-day fasting diet on weight loss and CAD risk factors in overweight and obese women. *J. Diabetes Metab. Disord.* 12, 4.
- Everard, A., Belzer, C., Geurts, L., Ouwerkerk, J.P., Druart, C., Bindels, L.B., Guiot, Y., Derrien, M., Muccioli, G.G., Delzenne, N.M., et al., 2013. Cross-talk between Akkermansia muciniphila and intestinal epithelium controls diet-induced obesity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 110, 9066–9071.
- Faris, M.A., Kacimi, S., Al-Kurd, R.A., Fararjeh, M.A., Bustanji, Y.K., Mohammad, M.K., Salem, M.L., 2012. Intermittent fasting during Ramadan attenuates proinflammatory cytokines and immune cells in healthy subjects. *Nutr. Res.* 32, 947–955.
- Farr, O.M., Tsoukas, M.A., Mantzoros, C.S., 2015. Leptin and the brain: influences on brain development, cognitive functioning and psychiatric disorders. *Metabolism* 64, 114–130.
- Farzi, A., Fröhlich, E.E., Holzer, P., 2018. Gut microbiota and the neuroendocrine system. *Neurotherapeutics* 15, 5–22.
- Farzi, A., Reichmann, F., Holzer, P., 2015a. The homeostatic role of neuropeptide Y in immune function and its impact on mood and behaviour. *Acta Physiol. (Oxf)* 213, 603–627.
- Farzi, A., Reichmann, F., Meintzer, A., Mayerhofer, R., Jain, P., Hassan, A.M., Fröhlich, E.E., Wagner, K., Painsipp, E., Rinner, B., et al., 2015b. Synergistic effects of NOD1 or NOD2 and TLR4 activation on mouse sickness behavior in relation to immune and brain activity markers. *Brain Behav. Immun.* 44, 106–120.
- Favennec, M., Hennart, B., Caiazza, R., Leloire, A., Yengo, L., Verbanck, M., Arredouani, A., Marre, M., Pigeyre, M., Bessedé, A., et al., 2015. The kynurenine pathway is activated in human obesity and shifted toward kynurenine monooxygenase activation. *Obesity (Silver Spring)* 23, 2066–2074.
- Federico, A., Dallio, M., Tolone, S., Gravina, A.G., Patrone, V., Romano, M., Tuccillo, C., Mozzillo, A.L., Amoroso, V., Misso, G., et al., 2016. Gastrointestinal hormones, intestinal microbiota and metabolic homeostasis in obese patients: effect of bariatric surgery. *In Vivo* 30, 321–330.
- Field, B.C., Chaudhri, O.B., Bloom, S.R., 2010. Bowels control brain: gut hormones and obesity. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* 6, 444–453.
- Finger, B.C., Dinan, T.G., Cryan, J.F., 2011. High-fat diet selectively protects against the effects of chronic social stress in the mouse. *Neuroscience* 192, 351–360.
- Fraumene, C., Manghina, V., Cadoni, E., Marongiu, F., Abbondio, M., Serra, M., Palomba, A., Tanca, A., Laconi, E., Uzzau, S., 2018. Caloric restriction promotes rapid expansion and long-lasting increase of Lactobacillus in the rat fecal microbiota. *Gut Microb.* 9, 104–114.
- Fröhlich, E.E., Farzi, A., Mayerhofer, R., Reichmann, F., Jačan, A., Wagner, B., Zinser, E., Bordag, N., Magnes, C., Fröhlich, E., et al., 2016. Cognitive impairment by antibiotic-induced gut dysbiosis: analysis of gut microbiota-brain communication. *Brain Behav. Immun.* 56, 140–155.
- Fu, M., Li, X., Zhang, M., Xian, Y., 2002. Increased expression of neuropeptide Y and its mRNA in STZ-diabetic rats. *Chin. Med. J.* 115, 690–695.
- Gainey, S.J., Kwakwa, K.A., Bray, J.K., Pillote, M.M., Tir, V.L., Towers, A.E., Freund, G.G., 2016. Short-term high-fat diet (HFD) induced anxiety-like behaviors and cognitive impairment are improved with treatment by glyburide. *Front. Behav. Neurosci.* 10, 156.
- Galligan, J.J., 2018. Beneficial actions of microbiota-derived tryptophan metabolites. *Neuro Gastroenterol. Motil.* 30.
- Gao, J., Xu, K., Liu, H., Liu, G., Bai, M., Peng, C., Li, T., Yin, Y., 2018. Impact of the gut microbiota on intestinal immunity mediated by tryptophan metabolism. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol* 8, 13.
- Garipey, G., Nitka, D., Schmitz, N., 2010. The association between obesity and anxiety disorders in the population: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int. J. Obes.* 34, 407–419.
- Geurts, L., Everard, A., Van Hul, M., Essaghir, A., Duparc, T., Matamoros, S., Plovier, H., Castel, J., Denis, R.G., Bergiers, M., et al., 2015. Adipose tissue NAPE-PLD controls fat mass development by altering the browning process and gut microbiota. *Nat. Commun.* 6, 6495.
- Ghoshal, S., Witta, J., Zhong, J., de Villiers, W., Eckhardt, E., 2009. Chylomicrons promote intestinal absorption of lipopolysaccharides. *J. Lipid Res.* 50, 90–97.
- Gomez, R., Vargas, C.R., Wajner, M., Barros, H.M., 2003. Lower in vivo brain extracellular GABA concentration in diabetic rats during forced swimming. *Brain Res.* 968, 281–284.
- Grasset, E., Puel, A., Charpentier, J., Collet, X., Christensen, J.E., Terce, F., Burcelin, R., 2017. A specific gut microbiota dysbiosis of type 2 diabetic mice induces GLP-1 resistance through an enteric NO-dependent and gut-brain axis mechanism. *Cell Metabol.* 25, 1075–1090 e1075.
- Groen, R.N., de Clercq, N.C., Nieuwoudorp, M., Hoenders, H.J.R., Groen, A.K., 2018. Gut microbiota, metabolism and psychopathology: a critical review and novel perspectives. *Crit. Rev. Clin. Lab Sci.* 55, 283–293.
- Halagappa, V.K., Guo, Z., Pearson, M., Matsuoka, Y., Cutler, R.G., Laferla, F.M., Mattson, M.P., 2007. Intermittent fasting and caloric restriction ameliorate age-related behavioral deficits in the triple-transgenic mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol. Dis.* 26, 212–220.
- Harris, M.L., Oldmeadow, C., Hure, A., Luu, J., Loxton, D., Attia, J., 2017. Stress increases the risk of type 2 diabetes onset in women: a 12-year longitudinal study using causal modelling. *PLoS One* 12, e0172126.
- Harvie, M.N., Pegington, M., Mattson, M.P., Frystyk, J., Dillon, B., Evans, G., Cuzick, J., Jebb, S.A., Martin, B., Cutler, R.G., et al., 2011. The effects of intermittent or continuous energy restriction on weight loss and metabolic disease risk markers: a randomized trial in young overweight women. *Int. J. Obes. (Lond)* 35, 714–727.
- Hassan, A.M., Jain, P., Reichmann, F., Mayerhofer, R., Farzi, A., Schuliger, R., Holzer, P.,

2014. Repeated predictable stress causes resilience against colitis-induced behavioral changes in mice. *Front. Behav. Neurosci.* 8, 386.
- Hassan, A.M., Mancano, G., Kashofer, K., Fröhlich, E.E., Matak, A., Mayerhofer, R., Reichmann, F., Olivares, M., Neyrinck, A.M., Delzenne, N.M., et al., 2018. High-fat diet induces depression-like behaviour in mice associated with changes in microbiome, neuropeptide Y, and brain metabolome. *Nutr. Neurosci.* 1–17.
- Hatori, M., Vollmers, C., Zarrinpar, A., DiTacchio, L., Bushong, E.A., Gill, S., Leblanc, M., Chaix, A., Joens, M., Fitzpatrick, J.A., et al., 2012. Time-restricted feeding without reducing caloric intake prevents metabolic diseases in mice fed a high-fat diet. *Cell Metabol.* 15, 848–860.
- Heilbronn, L.K., Smith, S.R., Martin, C.K., Anton, S.D., Ravussin, E., 2005. Alternate-day fasting in nonobese subjects: effects on body weight, body composition, and energy metabolism. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 81, 69–73.
- Heraclides, A., Chandola, T., Witte, D.R., Brunner, E.J., 2009. Psychosocial stress at work doubles the risk of type 2 diabetes in middle-aged women: evidence from the Whitehall II study. *Diabetes Care* 32, 2230–2235.
- Herrema, H., RG, L.J., Nieuwdorp, M., 2017. Emerging role of intestinal microbiota and microbial metabolites in metabolic control. *Diabetologia* 60, 613–617.
- Ho, N., Sommers, M.S., Lucki, I., 2013. Effects of diabetes on hippocampal neurogenesis: links to cognition and depression. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 37, 1346–1362.
- Holt, R.I., Bushe, C., Citrome, L., 2005. Diabetes and schizophrenia 2005: are we any closer to understanding the link? *J. Psychopharmacol.* 19, 56–65.
- Holt, R.I., de Groot, M., Lucki, I., Hunter, C.M., Sartorius, N., Golden, S.H., 2014. NIDDK international conference report on diabetes and depression: current understanding and future directions. *Diabetes Care* 37, 2067–2077.
- Holzer, P., 2008. The role of the vagus nerve in afferent signaling and homeostasis during visceral inflammation. In: In: Jancsó, G. (Ed.), *Neurogenic Inflammation in Health and Disease, Neuroimmune Biology*, vol. 8. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 321–338.
- Holzer, P., 2016. Neuropeptides, microbiota, and behavior. *Int. Rev. Neurobiol.* 131, 67–89.
- Holzer, P., Farzi, A., 2018. Peptide YY (PPY). In: *Reference Module in Biomedical Sciences, Encyclopedia of Endocrine Diseases*, second ed. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 1–7.
- Holzer, P., Farzi, A., Hassan, A.M., Zenz, G., Jacan, A., Reichmann, F., 2017. Visceral inflammation and immune activation stress the brain. *Front. Immunol.* 8, 1613.
- Holzer, P., Hassan, A.M., Jain, P., Reichmann, F., Farzi, A., 2015. Neuroimmune pharmacological approaches. *Curr. Opin. Pharmacol.* 25, 13–22.
- Horne, B.D., Muhlestein, J.B., Anderson, J.L., 2015. Health effects of intermittent fasting: hormesis or harm? A systematic review. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 102, 464–470.
- Hussin, N.M., Shahar, S., Teng, N.I., Ngah, W.Z., Das, S.K., 2013. Efficacy of fasting and calorie restriction (FCR) on mood and depression among ageing men. *J. Nutr. Health Aging* 17, 674–680.
- Jacka, F.N., Kremer, P.J., Berk, M., de Silva-Sanigorski, A.M., Moodie, M., Leslie, E.R., Pasco, J.A., Swinburn, B.A., 2011. A prospective study of diet quality and mental health in adolescents. *PLoS One* 6, e24805.
- Jacka, F.N., O'Neil, A., Opie, R., Itsiopoulos, C., Cotton, S., Mohebbi, M., Castle, D., Dash, S., Mihalopoulos, C., Chatterton, M.L., et al., 2017. A randomised controlled trial of dietary improvement for adults with major depression (the 'SMILES' trial). *BMC Med.* 15, 23.
- Jacobsen, S.H., Olesen, S.C., Dirksen, C., Jorgensen, N.B., Bojsen-Moller, K.N., Kielgast, U., Worm, D., Almdal, T., Naver, L.S., Hvolris, L.E., et al., 2012. Changes in gastrointestinal hormone responses, insulin sensitivity, and beta-cell function within 2 weeks after gastric bypass in non-diabetic subjects. *Obes. Surg.* 22, 1084–1096.
- Janik, R., Thomason, L.A.M., Stanisiz, A.M., Forsythe, P., Bienenstock, J., Stanisiz, G.J., 2016. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy reveals oral Lactobacillus promotion of increases in brain GABA, N-acetyl aspartate and glutamate. *Neuroimage* 125, 988–995.
- Jayaraman, A., Pike, C.J., 2014. Alzheimer's disease and type 2 diabetes: multiple mechanisms contribute to interactions. *Curr. Diabetes Rep.* 14, 476.
- Jennis, M., Cavanaugh, C.R., Leo, G.C., Mabius, J.R., Lenhard, J., Hornby, P.J., 2018. Microbiota-derived tryptophan indoles increase after gastric bypass surgery and reduce intestinal permeability in vitro and in vivo. *Neuro Gastroenterol. Motil.* 30.
- Jiang, H., Ling, Z., Zhang, Y., Mao, H., Ma, Z., Yin, Y., Wang, W., Tang, W., Tan, Z., Shi, J., et al., 2015. Altered fecal microbiota composition in patients with major depressive disorder. *Brain Behav. Immun.* 48, 186–194.
- Jin, U.H., Lee, S.O., Sridharan, G., Lee, K., Davidson, L.A., Jayaraman, A., Chapkin, R.S., Alaniz, R., Safe, S., 2014. Microbiome-derived tryptophan metabolites and their aryl hydrocarbon receptor-dependent agonist and antagonist activities. *Mol. Pharmacol.* 85, 777–788.
- Jung, S.J., Woo, H.T., Cho, S., Park, K., Jeong, S., Lee, Y.J., Kang, D., Shin, A., 2017. Association between body size, weight change and depression: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 211, 14–21.
- Kamble, M., Gupta, R., Rehan, H.S., Gupta, L.K., 2016. Neurobehavioral effects of liraglutide and sitagliptin in experimental models. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 774, 64–70.
- Kawakami, N., Takatsuka, N., Shimizu, H., Ishibashi, H., 1999. Depressive symptoms and occurrence of type 2 diabetes among Japanese men. *Diabetes Care* 22, 1071–1076.
- Kelly, J.R., Borre, Y., C, O.B., Patterson, E., Al Aidy, S., Deane, J., Kennedy, P.J., Beers, S., Scott, K., Moloney, G., et al., 2016. Transferring the blues: depression-associated gut microbiota induces neurobehavioural changes in the rat. *J. Psychiatr. Res.* 82, 109–118.
- Kiecolt-Glaser, J.K., Habash, D.L., Fagundes, C.P., Andridge, R., Peng, J., Malarkey, W.B., Belury, M.A., 2015. Daily stressors, past depression, and metabolic responses to high-fat meals: a novel path to obesity. *Biol. Psychiatry* 77, 653–660.
- Klempel, M.C., Kroeger, C.M., Bhutani, S., Trepanowski, J.F., Varady, K.A., 2012. Intermittent fasting combined with calorie restriction is effective for weight loss and cardio-protection in obese women. *Nutr. J.* 11, 98.
- Kowalchuk, C., Castellani, L., Chintoh, A., Remington, G., Giacca, A., Hahn, M., 2018. Antipsychotics and glucose metabolism: how brain and body collide. *Am. J. Physiol. Endocrinol. Metab.* (in press).
- Krabbe, K.S., Nielsen, A.R., Krogh-Madsen, R., Plomgaard, P., Rasmussen, P., Erikstrup, C., Fischer, C.P., Lindegaard, B., Petersen, A.M., Taudorf, S., et al., 2007. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia* 50, 431–438.
- Le Bastard, Q., Al-Ghalith, G.A., Grégoire, M., Chapelet, G., Javaudin, F., Dailly, E., Batard, E., Knights, D., Montassier, E., 2018. Systematic review: human gut dysbiosis induced by non-antibiotic prescription medications. *Aliment Pharmacol. Ther.* 47, 332–345.
- Lee, H.U., McPherson, Z.E., Tan, B., Korecka, A., Pettersson, S., 2017. Host-microbiome interactions: the aryl hydrocarbon receptor and the central nervous system. *J. Mol. Med. (Berl.)* 95, 29–39.
- Lee, J., Duan, W., Mattson, M.P., 2002. Evidence that brain-derived neurotrophic factor is required for basal neurogenesis and mediates, in part, the enhancement of neurogenesis by dietary restriction in the hippocampus of adult mice. *J. Neurochem.* 82, 1367–1375.
- Lee, J., Herman, J.P., Mattson, M.P., 2000. Dietary restriction selectively decreases glucocorticoid receptor expression in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex of rats. *Exp. Neurol.* 166, 435–441.
- Liang, L., Zhou, H., Zhang, S., Yuan, J., Wu, H., 2017. Effects of gut microbiota disturbance induced in early life on the expression of extrasynaptic GABA-A receptor alpha5 and delta subunits in the hippocampus of adult rats. *Brain Res. Bull.* 135, 113–119.
- Li, G., Xie, C., Lu, S., Nichols, R.G., Tian, Y., Li, L., Patel, D., Ma, Y., Brocker, C.N., Yan, T., et al., 2017. Intermittent fasting promotes white adipose browning and decreases obesity by shaping the gut microbiota. *Cell Metabol.* 26, 672–685.
- Lin, E.J., Sun, M., Choi, E.Y., Magee, D., Stets, C.W., Doring, M.J., 2015. Social overcrowding as a chronic stress model that increases adiposity in mice. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* 51, 318–330.
- Lu, B., Nagappan, G., Lu, Y., 2014. BDNF and synaptic plasticity, cognitive function, and dysfunction. *Handb. Exp. Pharmacol.* 220, 223–250.
- Luczynski, P., McVey Neufeld, K.A., Oriach, C.S., Clarke, G., Dinan, T.G., Cryan, J.F., 2016. Growing up in a bubble: using germ-free animals to assess the influence of the gut microbiota on brain and behavior. *Int. J. Neuropsychopharmacol.* 19, pyw020.
- Luppino, F.S., de Wit, L.M., Bouvy, P.F., Stijnen, T., Cuijpers, P., Penninx, B.W., Zitman, F.G., 2010. Overweight, obesity, and depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Arch. Gen. Psychiatr.* 67, 220–229.
- Luscher, B., Shen, Q., Sahir, N., 2011. The GABAergic deficit hypothesis of major depressive disorder. *Mol. Psychiatr.* 16, 383–406.
- Ma, K., Xu, A., Cui, S., Sun, M.R., Xue, Y.C., Wang, J.H., 2016. Impaired GABA synthesis, uptake and release are associated with depression-like behaviors induced by chronic mild stress. *Transl. Psychiatry* 6, e910.
- Magdy, Y.M., El-Kharashi, O.A., Nabih, E.S., Shaker, S.M., Abd-Elaziz, L.F., Aboul-Fotouh, S., 2017. Potential involvement of JNK1 repression in the hepatic effect of sitagliptin and metformin in rats subjected to high fat diet and chronic mild distress. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 85, 225–238.
- Maier, L., Pruteanu, M., Kuhn, M., Zeller, G., Telzerow, A., Anderson, E.E., Brochado, A.R., Fernandez, K.C., Dose, H., Mori, H., et al., 2018. Extensive impact of non-antibiotic drugs on human gut bacteria. *Nature* 555, 623–628.
- Maniam, J., Morris, M.J., 2010. Long-term postpartum anxiety and depression-like behavior in mother rats subjected to maternal separation are ameliorated by palatable high fat diet. *Behav. Brain Res.* 208, 72–79.
- Mannan, M., Mamun, A., Doi, S., Clavarino, A., 2016. Prospective associations between depression and obesity for adolescent males and females - a systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *PLoS One* 11, e0157240.
- Mansur, R.B., Ahmed, J., Cha, D.S., Woldeyohannes, H.O., Subramaniapillai, M., Lovshin, J., Lee, J.G., Lee, J.H., Brietzke, E., Reininghaus, E.Z., et al., 2017. Liraglutide promotes improvements in objective measures of cognitive dysfunction in individuals with mood disorders: a pilot, open-label study. *J. Affect. Disord.* 207, 114–120.
- Marchelek-Mysliwiec, M., Dutkiewicz, G., Wisniewska, M., Pietrzak-Nowacka, M., Ciechanowski, K., 2013. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor: a new face of metabolic disorders. *Ann. Clin. Biochem.* 50, 189–190.
- Marques, T.M., Patterson, E., Wall, R., O'Sullivan, O., Fitzgerald, G.F., Cotter, P.D., Dinan, T.G., Cryan, J.F., Ross, R.P., Stanton, C., 2016. Influence of GABA and GABA-producing Lactobacillus brevis DPC 6108 on the development of diabetes in a streptozotocin rat model. *Benef. Microbes* 7, 409–420.
- Mattson, M.P., Longo, V.D., Harvie, M., 2017. Impact of intermittent fasting on health and disease processes. *Ageing Res. Rev.* 39, 46–58.
- Mayer, E.A., 2011. Gut feelings: the emerging biology of gut-brain communication. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 12, 453–466.
- Melamed, S., Shirom, A., Toker, S., Shapira, I., 2006. Burnout and risk of type 2 diabetes: a prospective study of apparently healthy employed persons. *Psychosom. Med.* 68, 863–869.
- Million, M., Lagier, J.C., Yahav, D., Paul, M., 2013. Gut bacterial microbiota and obesity. *Clin. Microbiol. Infect.* 19, 305–313.
- Molteni, R., Wu, A., Vaynman, S., Ying, Z., Barnard, R.J., Gomez-Pinilla, F., 2004. Exercise reverses the harmful effects of consumption of a high-fat diet on synaptic and behavioral plasticity associated to the action of brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Neuroscience* 123, 429–440.
- Morris, M.J., Chen, H., Watts, R., Shulkes, A., Cameron-Smith, D., 2008. Brain neuropeptide Y and CCK and peripheral adipokin receptors: temporal response in obesity induced by palatable diet. *Int. J. Obes.* 32, 249–258.
- Moyer, B.J., Rojas, I.Y., Kerley-Hamilton, J.S., Hazlett, H.F., Nemani, K.V., Trask, H.W., West, R.J., Lupien, L.E., Collins, A.J., Ringelberg, C.S., et al., 2016. Inhibition of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor prevents Western diet-induced obesity. Model for AHR activation by kynurenine via oxidized-LDL, TLR2/4, TGFbeta, and Idol1. *Toxicol.*

- Appl. Pharmacol. 300, 13–24.
- Muccioli, G.G., Naslain, D., Bäckhed, F., Reigstad, C.S., Lambert, D.M., Delzenne, N.M., Cani, P.D., 2010. The endocannabinoid system links gut microbiota to adipogenesis. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* 6, 392.
- Mukherjee, S., Decina, P., Bocola, V., Saraceni, F., Scapicchio, P.L., 1996. Diabetes mellitus in schizophrenic patients. *Compr. Psychiatr.* 37, 68–73.
- Muriach, M., Flores-Bellver, M., Romero, F.J., Barcia, J.M., 2014. Diabetes and the brain: oxidative stress, inflammation, and autophagy. *Oxid Med Cell Longev* 2014, 102158.
- Naseribafrouei, A., Hestad, K., Avershina, E., Sekelja, M., Linlokken, A., Wilson, R., Rudi, K., 2014. Correlation between the human fecal microbiota and depression. *Neuro Gastroenterol. Motil.* 26, 1155–1162.
- Naughton, M., Dinan, T.G., Scott, L.V., 2014. Corticotropin-releasing hormone and the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis in psychiatric disease. *Handb. Clin. Neurol.* 124, 69–91.
- O'Connor, J.C., Andre, C., Wang, Y., Lawson, M.A., Szegedi, S.S., Lestage, J., Castanon, N., Kelley, K.W., Dantzer, R., 2009. Interferon-gamma and tumor necrosis factor- α mediate the upregulation of indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase and the induction of depressive-like behavior in mice in response to bacillus Calmette-Guerin. *J. Neurosci.* 29, 4200–4209.
- OMahony, S.M., Clarke, G., Borre, Y.E., Dinan, T.G., Cryan, J.F., 2015. Serotonin, tryptophan metabolism and the brain-gut-microbiome axis. *Behav. Brain Res.* 277, 32–48.
- Park, H.R., Park, M., Choi, J., Park, K.Y., Chung, H.Y., Lee, J., 2010. A high-fat diet impairs neurogenesis: involvement of lipid peroxidation and brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Neurosci. Lett.* 482, 235–239.
- Park, S., Bae, J.H., 2015. Probiotics for weight loss: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutr. Res.* 35, 566–575.
- Petrou, M., Pop-Busui, R., Foerster, B.R., Edden, R.A., Callaghan, B.C., Harte, S.E., Harris, R.E., Clauw, D.J., Feldman, E.L., 2012. Altered excitation-inhibition balance in the brain of patients with diabetic neuropathy. *Acad. Radiol.* 19, 607–612.
- Pingitore, A., Chambers, E.S., Hill, T., Maldonado, I.R., Liu, B., Bewick, G., Morrison, D.J., Preston, T., Wallis, G.A., Tedford, C., et al., 2017. The diet-derived short chain fatty acid propionate improves beta-cell function in humans and stimulates insulin secretion from human islets in vitro. *Diabetes Obes. Metabol.* 19, 257–265.
- Pokusaeva, K., Johnson, C., Luk, B., Uribe, G., Fu, Y., Oezguen, N., Matsunami, R.K., Lugo, M., Major, A., Mori-Akiyama, Y., et al., 2017. GABA-producing *Bifidobacterium dentium* modulates visceral sensitivity in the intestine. *Neuro Gastroenterol. Motil.* 29.
- Rabot, S., Membrez, M., Bruneau, A., Gerard, P., Harach, T., Moser, M., Raymond, F., Mansourian, R., Chou, C.J., 2010. Germ-free C57BL/6J mice are resistant to high-fat-diet-induced insulin resistance and have altered cholesterol metabolism. *Faseb. J.* 24, 4948–4959.
- Räikkönen, K., Matthews, K.A., Kuller, L.H., 2007. Depressive symptoms and stressful life events predict metabolic syndrome among middle-aged women: a comparison of World Health Organization, Adult Treatment Panel III, and International Diabetes Foundation definitions. *Diabetes Care* 30, 872–877.
- Ramracheya, R.D., McCulloch, L.J., Clark, A., Wiggins, D., Johannessen, H., Olsen, M.K., Cai, X., Zhao, C.M., Chen, D., Rorsman, P., 2016. PYY-dependent restoration of impaired insulin and glucagon secretion in type 2 diabetes following Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery. *Cell Rep.* 15, 944–950.
- Razzoli, M., Bartolomucci, A., 2016. The dichotomous effect of chronic stress on obesity. *Trends Endocrinol. Metabol.* 27, 504–515.
- Razzoli, M., McCallum, J., Gurney, A., Engeland, W.C., Bartolomucci, A., 2015a. Chronic stress aggravates glucose intolerance in leptin receptor-deficient (db/db) mice. *Genes Nutr* 10, 458.
- Razzoli, M., Pearson, C., Crow, S., Bartolomucci, A., 2017. Stress, overeating, and obesity: insights from human studies and preclinical models. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 76, 154–162.
- Razzoli, M., Sanghez, V., Bartolomucci, A., 2015b. Chronic subordination stress induces hyperphagia and disrupts eating behavior in mice modeling binge-eating-like disorder. *Front Nutr* 1 00030.
- Redman, L.M., Martin, C.K., Williamson, D.A., Ravussin, E., 2008. Effect of caloric restriction in non-obese humans on physiological, psychological and behavioral outcomes. *Physiol. Behav.* 94, 643–648.
- Reichmann, F., Holzer, P., 2016. Neuropeptide Y: a stressful review. *Neuropeptides* 55, 99–109.
- Roh, E., Kwak, S.H., Jung, H.S., Cho, Y.M., Pak, Y.K., Park, K.S., Kim, S.Y., Lee, H.K., 2015. Serum aryl hydrocarbon receptor ligand activity is associated with insulin resistance and resulting type 2 diabetes. *Acta Diabetol.* 52, 489–495.
- Rooks, M.G., Garrett, W.S., 2016. Gut microbiota, metabolites and host immunity. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 16, 341–352.
- Rosmond, R., 2003. Stress induced disturbances of the HPA axis: a pathway to Type 2 diabetes? *Med. Sci. Mon. Int. Med. J. Exp. Clin. Res.* 9, RA35–39.
- Rothhammer, V., Mascanfroni, I.D., Bunse, L., Takenaka, M.C., Kenison, J.E., Mayo, L., Chao, C.C., Patel, B., Yan, R., Blain, M., et al., 2016. Type 1 interferons and microbial metabolites of tryptophan modulate astrocyte activity and central nervous system inflammation via the aryl hydrocarbon receptor. *Nat. Med.* 22, 586–597.
- Rothman, S.M., Griffioen, K.J., Wan, R., Mattson, M.P., 2012. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor as a regulator of systemic and brain energy metabolism and cardiovascular health. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1264, 49–63.
- Roy, T., Lloyd, C.E., 2012. Epidemiology of depression and diabetes: a systematic review. *J. Affect. Disord.* 142 (Suppl. 1), S8–S21.
- Ruiz, A., Cerdó, T., Jáuregui, R., Pieper, D.H., Marcos, A., Clemente, A., García, F., Margolles, A., Ferrer, M., Campoy, C., et al., 2017. One-year calorie restriction impacts gut microbial composition but not its metabolic performance in obese adolescents. *Environ. Microbiol.* 19, 1536–1551.
- Ruohonen, S.T., Pesonen, U., Moritz, N., Kaipio, K., Roytta, M., Koulou, M., Savontaus, E., 2008. Transgenic mice overexpressing neuropeptide Y in noradrenergic neurons: a novel model of increased adiposity and impaired glucose tolerance. *Diabetes* 57, 1517–1525.
- Ryan, M.C., Thakore, J.H., 2002. Physical consequences of schizophrenia and its treatment: the metabolic syndrome. *Life Sci.* 71, 239–257.
- Sam, A.H., Gunner, D.J., King, A., Persaud, S.J., Brooks, L., Hostomska, K., Ford, H.E., Liu, B., Ghatei, M.A., Bloom, S.R., et al., 2012. Selective ablation of peptide YY cells in adult mice reveals their role in beta cell survival. *Gastroenterology* 143, 459–468.
- Samah, S., Ramasamy, K., Lim, S.M., Neoh, C.F., 2016. Probiotics for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Res. Clin. Pract.* 118, 172–182.
- Samuel, B.S., Shaito, A., Motoike, T., Rey, F.E., Bäckhed, F., Manchester, J.K., Hammer, R.E., Williams, S.C., Crowley, J., Yanagisawa, M., et al., 2008. Effects of the gut microbiota on host adiposity are modulated by the short-chain fatty-acid binding G protein-coupled receptor, Gpr41. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 105, 16767–16772.
- Sánchez-Villegas, A., Martínez-González, M.A., Estruch, R., Salas-Salvado, J., Corella, D., Covas, M.I., Aros, F., Romaguera, D., Gomez-Gracia, E., Lapetra, J., et al., 2013. Mediterranean dietary pattern and depression: the PREDIMED randomized trial. *BMC Med.* 11, 208.
- Sánchez-Villegas, A., Toledo, E., de Irala, J., Ruiz-Canela, M., Pla-Vidal, J., Martínez-González, M.A., 2012. Fast-food and commercial baked goods consumption and the risk of depression. *Publ. Health Nutr.* 15, 424–432.
- Sandoval-Salazar, C., Ramirez-Emiliano, J., Trejo-Bahana, A., Oviedo-Solis, C.I., Solis-Ortiz, M.S., 2016. A high-fat diet decreases GABA concentration in the frontal cortex and hippocampus of rats. *Biol. Res.* 49 15-016-0075-0076.
- Sanghez, V., Razzoli, M., Carobbio, S., Campbell, M., McCallum, J., Cero, C., Ceresini, G., Cabassi, A., Govoni, P., Franceschini, P., et al., 2013. Psychosocial stress induces hyperphagia and exacerbates diet-induced insulin resistance and the manifestations of the Metabolic Syndrome. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* 38, 2933–2942.
- Schéle, E., Grahnmö, L., Anesten, F., Hallen, A., Bäckhed, F., Jansson, J.O., 2013. The gut microbiota reduces leptin sensitivity and the expression of the obesity-suppressing neuropeptides proglucagon (Gcg) and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (Bdnf) in the central nervous system. *Endocrinology* 154, 3643–3651.
- Schoenfeld, T.J., Cameron, H.A., 2015. Adult neurogenesis and mental illness. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 40, 113–128.
- Schroeder, F.A., Lin, C.L., Crusio, W.E., Akbarian, S., 2007. Antidepressant-like effects of the histone deacetylase inhibitor, sodium butyrate, in the mouse. *Biol. Psychiatry* 62, 55–64.
- Schwarcz, R., Bruno, J.P., Muchowski, P.J., Wu, H.Q., 2012. Kynurenes in the mammalian brain: when physiology meets pathology. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 13, 465–477.
- Schwartz, M.W., Baskin, D.G., Bukowski, T.R., Kuijper, J.L., Foster, D., Lasser, G., Prunkard, D.E., Porte Jr., D., Woods, S.C., Seeley, R.J., et al., 1996. Specificity of leptin action on elevated blood glucose levels and hypothalamic neuropeptide Y gene expression in ob/ob mice. *Diabetes* 45, 531–535.
- Semenkovich, K., Brown, M.E., Svrakic, D.M., Lustman, P.J., 2015. Depression in type 2 diabetes mellitus: prevalence, impact, and treatment. *Drugs* 75, 577–587.
- Shalaby, A., Kamal, S., 2009. Effect of Escitalopram on GABA level and anti-oxidant markers in prefrontal cortex and nucleus accumbens of chronic mild stress-exposed albino rats. *Int J Physiol Pathophysiol Pharmacol* 1, 154–161.
- Sharma, S., Fulton, S., 2013. Diet-induced obesity promotes depressive-like behaviour that is associated with neural adaptations in brain reward circuitry. *Int. J. Obes.* 37, 382–389.
- Shi, Y.C., Lin, S., Castillo, L., Aljanova, A., Enriquez, R.F., Nguyen, A.D., Baldock, P.A., Zhang, L., Bijker, M.S., Macia, L., et al., 2011. Peripheral-specific Y2 receptor knockdown protects mice from high-fat diet-induced obesity. *Obesity (Silver Spring)* 19, 2137–2148.
- Singh, R., Kaushik, S., Wang, Y., Xiang, Y., Novak, I., Komatsu, M., Tanaka, K., Cuervo, A.M., Czaja, M.J., 2009. Autophagy regulates lipid metabolism. *Nature* 458, 1131–1135.
- Sipols, A.J., Baskin, D.G., Schwartz, M.W., 1995. Effect of intracerebroventricular insulin infusion on diabetic hyperphagia and hypothalamic neuropeptide gene expression. *Diabetes* 44, 147–151.
- Slyepchenko, A., Maes, M., Jacka, F.N., Kohler, C.A., Barichello, T., McIntyre, R.S., Berk, M., Grande, I., Foster, J.A., Vieta, E., et al., 2017. Gut microbiota, bacterial translocation, and interactions with diet: pathophysiological links between major depressive disorder and non-communicable medical comorbidities. *Psychother. Psychosom.* 86, 31–46.
- Smith, K.J., Beland, M., Clyde, M., Garipey, G., Page, V., Badawi, G., Rabasa-Lhoret, R., Schmitz, N., 2013. Association of diabetes with anxiety: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Psychosom. Res.* 74, 89–99.
- Soto, M., Herzog, C., Pacheco, J.A., Fujisaka, S., Bullock, K., Clish, C.B., Kahn, C.R., 2018. Gut microbiota modulate neurobehavior through changes in brain insulin sensitivity and metabolism. *Mol. Psychiatr.* (in press).
- Stuart, M.J., Baune, B.T., 2012. Depression and type 2 diabetes: inflammatory mechanisms of a psychoneuroendocrine co-morbidity. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 36, 658–676.
- Sun, L., Xie, C., Wang, G., Wu, Y., Wu, Q., Wang, X., Liu, J., Deng, Y., Xia, J., Chen, B., et al., 2018. Gut microbiota and intestinal FXR mediate the clinical benefits of metformin. *Nat. Med.* (in press).
- Sun, W.W., Zhu, P., Shi, Y.C., Zhang, C.L., Huang, X.F., Liang, S.Y., Song, Z.Y., Lin, S., 2017. Current views on neuropeptide Y and diabetes-related atherosclerosis. *Diabetes Vasc. Dis. Res.* 14, 277–284.
- Sutaria, S., Devakumar, D., Yasuda, S.S., Das, S., Saxena, S., 2018. Is obesity associated with depression in children? Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Arch. Dis. Child* (in press).
- Suwa, M., Kishimoto, H., Nofuji, Y., Nakano, H., Sasaki, H., Radak, Z., Kumagai, S., 2006. Serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor level is increased and associated with

- obesity in newly diagnosed female patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Metab. Clin. Exp.* 55, 852–857.
- Sweeney, P., O'Hara, K., Xu, Z., Yang, Y., 2017. HFD-induced energy states-dependent bidirectional control of anxiety levels in mice. *Int. J. Obes. (Lond)* 41, 1237–1245.
- Thangaraju, M., Cresci, G.A., Liu, K., Ananth, S., Gnanaprakasam, J.P., Browning, D.D., Mellinger, J.D., Smith, S.B., Digby, G.J., Lambert, N.A., et al., 2009. GPR109A is a G-protein-coupled receptor for the bacterial fermentation product butyrate and functions as a tumor suppressor in colon. *Cancer Res.* 69, 2826–2832.
- Tran, K.L., Park, Y.I., Pandya, S., Muliylil, N.J., Jensen, B.D., Huynh, K., Nguyen, Q.T., 2017. Overview of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists for the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes. *Am Health Drug Benefits* 10, 178–188.
- Ueki, K., Kondo, T., Kahn, C.R., 2004. Suppressor of cytokine signaling 1 (SOCS-1) and SOCS-3 cause insulin resistance through inhibition of tyrosine phosphorylation of insulin receptor substrate proteins by discrete mechanisms. *Mol. Cell Biol.* 24, 5434–5446.
- Valdearcos, M., Robblee, M.M., Benjamin, D.I., Nomura, D.K., Xu, A.W., Koliwad, S.K., 2014. Microglia dictate the impact of saturated fat consumption on hypothalamic inflammation and neuronal function. *Cell Rep.* 9, 2124–2138.
- Valvassori, S.S., Varela, R.B., Arent, C.O., Dal-Pont, G.C., Bobsin, T.S., Budni, J., Reus, G.Z., Quevedo, J., 2014. Sodium butyrate functions as an antidepressant and improves cognition with enhanced neurotrophic expression in models of maternal deprivation and chronic mild stress. *Curr. Neurovascular Res.* 11, 359–366.
- van Bussel, F.C., Backes, W.H., Hofman, P.A., Puts, N.A., Edden, R.A., van Boxtel, M.P., Schram, M.T., Stehouwer, C.D., Wildberger, J.E., Jansen, J.F., 2016. Increased GABA concentrations in type 2 diabetes mellitus are related to lower cognitive functioning. *Medicine* 95 e4803.
- Van Gaal, L.F., Rissanen, A.M., Scheen, A.J., Ziegler, O., Rossner, S., 2005. Effects of the cannabinoid 1 receptor blocker rimonabant on weight reduction and cardiovascular risk factors in overweight patients: 1 year experience from the RIO-Europe study. *Lancet* 365, 1389–1397.
- Varady, K.A., Bhutani, S., Klempel, M.C., Kroeger, C.M., Trepanowski, J.F., Haus, J.M., Hoddy, K.K., Calvo, Y., 2013. Alternate day fasting for weight loss in normal weight and overweight subjects: a randomized controlled trial. *Nutr. J.* 12, 146.
- Vogelzangs, N., Kritchevsky, S.B., Beekman, A.T., Newman, A.B., Satterfield, S., Simonsick, E.M., Yaffe, K., Harris, T.B., Penninx, B.W., 2008. Depressive symptoms and change in abdominal obesity in older persons. *Arch. Gen. Psychiatr.* 65, 1386–1393.
- Wang, J., He, M., 2015. Levels of serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor in Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with and without depressive symptoms. *Acta Biochim. Biophys. Sin.* 47, 137–138.
- Wang, S., Huang, M., You, X., Zhao, J., Chen, L., Wang, L., Luo, L., Chen, Y., 2018. Gut microbiota mediates the anti-obesity effect of calorie restriction in mice. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 13037.
- Weina, H., Yuhu, N., Christian, H., Birong, L., Feiyu, S., Le, W., 2018. Liraglutide attenuates the depressive- and anxiety-like behaviour in the corticosterone induced depression model via improving hippocampal neural plasticity. *Brain Res.* 1694, 55–62.
- Williams, L.J., Pasco, J.A., Henry, M.J., Jacka, F.N., Dodd, S., Nicholson, G.C., Kotowicz, M.A., Berk, M., 2009. Lifetime psychiatric disorders and body composition: a population-based study. *J. Affect. Disord.* 118, 173–179.
- Winer, D.A., Luck, H., Tsai, S., Winer, S., 2016. The intestinal immune system in obesity and insulin resistance. *Cell Metabol.* 23, 413–426.
- Wing, R.R., Marcus, M.D., Blair, E.H., Epstein, L.H., Burton, L.R., 1990. Depressive symptomatology in obese adults with type II diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 13, 170–172.
- Yirmiya, R., Rimmerman, N., Reshef, R., 2015. Depression as a microglial disease. *Trends Neurosci.* 38, 637–658.
- Yu, M., Zhang, X., Lu, F., Fang, L., 2015. Depression and risk for diabetes: a meta-analysis. *Can. J. Diabetes* 39, 266–272.
- Yunes, R.A., Poluektova, E.U., Dyachkova, M.S., Klimina, K.M., Kovtun, A.S., Averina, O.V., Orlova, V.S., Danilenko, V.N., 2016. GABA production and structure of gadB/gadC genes in *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* strains from human microbiota. *Anaerobe* 42, 197–204.
- Zarrinpar, A., Chaix, A., Yooseph, S., Panda, S., 2014. Diet and feeding pattern affect the diurnal dynamics of the gut microbiome. *Cell Metabol.* 20, 1006–1017.
- Zemdegs, J., Quesseveur, G., Jarriault, D., Penicaud, L., Fioramonti, X., Guiard, B.P., 2016. High-fat diet-induced metabolic disorders impairs 5-HT function and anxiety-like behavior in mice. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 173, 2095–2110.
- Zhang, C., Li, S., Yang, L., Huang, P., Li, W., Wang, S., Zhao, G., Zhang, M., Pang, X., Yan, Z., et al., 2013. Structural modulation of gut microbiota in life-long calorie-restricted mice. *Nat. Commun.* 4, 2163.
- Zhang, L., Lee, I.C., Enriquez, R.F., Lau, J., Vahatalo, L.H., Baldock, P.A., Savontaus, E., Herzog, H., 2014. Stress- and diet-induced fat gain is controlled by NPY in catecholaminergic neurons. *Mol. Metab.* 3, 581–591.
- Zheng, P., Zeng, B., Zhou, C., Liu, M., Fang, Z., Xu, X., Zeng, L., Chen, J., Fan, S., Du, X., et al., 2016. Gut microbiome remodeling induces depressive-like behaviors through a pathway mediated by the host's metabolism. *Mol. Psychiatr.* 21, 786–796.
- Zheng, X., Wang, S., Jia, W., 2018. Calorie restriction and its impact on gut microbial composition and global metabolism. *Front. Med. (in press)*.
- Zhu, P., Sun, W., Zhang, C., Song, Z., Lin, S., 2016. The role of neuropeptide Y in the pathophysiology of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. *Int. J. Cardiol.* 220, 235–241.